

The National Pledge

Nigeria, we hail thee,
Our own dear native land,
Though tribe and tongue may differ,
In brotherhood we stand,
Nigerians all, and proud to serve
Our sovereign Motherland.

Our flag shall be a symbol
That truth and justice reign,
In peace or battle honored,
And this we count as gain,
To hand on to our children
A banner without stain.

The National Pledge

I pledge to Nigeria, my country
To be faithful, loyal, and honest,
To serve Nigeria with all my strength,
To defend her unity,
And uphold her honor and glory,
So help me God.

**His Excellency
Alh. Bola Ahmed Tinubu
President
Federal Republic of Nigeria**

Dr Dauda Lawal
Executive Governor, Zamfara State
Special Guest of Honour

Alh. Wadatau Madawaki

Commission Of Education, Science And Technology Zamfara State

Guest Of Honour

Guest of Honour
Honorable Abdulmalik Zubairu
Member Representing Bungudu Federal
Constituency Zamfara State

Alhaji Attahiru M. Ahmad
Emir of Zamfara Anka & Chairman Zamfara State Council of Chiefs,
Zamfara State, Nigeria
Royal Father of The Day

Prof. M. G. Abubakar
Vice Chancellor, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State
Chief Host

Dr Umar Sodangi
Dean, Faculty of Education
Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State
Host

Prof. L.S. Bilbis
Former Vice Chancellor Usman Danfodio University Sokoto

Amb. T.Y Buratai (Lt. Gen. Rtd.)
NAM OMM (BR) GSS psc (+) FCMH FNHAM BA (Hons) MA MPhil PhD
Nigerian Ambassador Extraordinary and Plenipotentiary to Republic of Benin

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Programme of Events

DAY 1: Tuesday, 25th February, 2025		
1	Arrivals	9:00 am- 10:00am
2	National Anthem	10:00am – 10:05am
3	Opening Prayers	10:05am – 10:10am
4	Introduction of Dignitaries	10:10am – 10:20am
5	Welcome Address by the Host/Dean, Dr. Umar Sodangi	10:20am – 10:30am
6	Remark by the Chief Host/Vice Chancellor, Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State Prof. M. G. Abubakar	10:30am – 10:40am
7	Remark by the Chairman, Prof. L.S Bilbis	10:40am – 10:45am
8	Citation / Key Note Address: Amb. T.Y. Buratai	10:45am – 11:15am
9	Citation/ Lead Paper presentation (I): Dr. Ahmad Rufa'i	11:15am – 11:45pm
10	Citation/ Lead Paper presentation (II): Prof. H. I. Bayero	11:45am – 12:15pm
11	Citation/ Lead Paper presentation (III): Dr. Akor Linus	12:15pm – 12:45pm
12	Presentation of Awards	12:45pm – 1:10pm
13	Remark by The Royal Father: Alhaji Attahiru M. Ahmed	1:10pm-1:20pm
14	Remark by the Governor: Dr. Dauda Lawal	1:20pm-1:30pm
15	Vote of Thanks by the LOC, Chairman Prof. Bashir Suleiman	1:30pm -1:40pm
16	Closing Prayers	1:40pm -1:45pm
17	National Anthem	1:45pm - 1:50pm
18	Departure of Dignitaries	1:50pm - 2:00pm
19	Lunch	2:00pm - 2:15pm
20	Parallel/Technical Session	2:15pm - 3:30pm
21	Cocktail	3:30pm-5:00pm
DAY 2: Wednesday, 26th February, 2025		
22	Arrival of Participants	8:30am - 9:00am
23	Parallel/Technical Session	9:00am - 10:00am
24	Break fast	10:00am - 10:30am
25	Parallel/Technical Session	10:30am - 1:30pm
26	Lunch	1:30pm - 2:00pm
27	Parallel/Technical Session	2:00pm - 3:00pm
28	Closing Ceremony	3:00pm – 5:00pm
DAY 3: Thursday, 27th February, 2025		
29	Departure	10:00am

ABSTRACTS

GROUP I: EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS (A), FOE LECTURE ROOM 1			
S/N	ABSTRACT CODE	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1	2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P01	Abdullahi, B. & Soye, S. H. Access, Equity and Quality Basic Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria	25
2	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P02	Ibrahim A. Impacts of Insecurity on the Secondary Schools Administration in Birnin Gwari Education Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria	26
3	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P03	Maifata, S. A., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. Insecurity and Educational Inequality: Challenges to Quality Learning in Conflict Affected Regions of Nigeria	27
4	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P04	Shehu, S. A. & Bukhari, B. Adoption Challenges of the Nigeria Learning Passport Digital Learning Platform Among Upper Basic Education Teachers in Insecurity-Prone Regions of Northwest Nigeria	28
5	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P05	Shehu, S. A. & Nasiru, M. G. Exploring Access, Equity, and Quality in Early Childhood Education in Nigeria Amidst In-Security Challenges	29
6	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P06	Bala, I., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. Impact of Insecurity on Educational Access and Social Mobility in Nigeria	30
7	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P07	Murtala, S., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. The Role of Government and Community Interventions in Addressing Educational Barriers Amid the Era of Insecurity in Nigeria	31
8	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P08	Ashiru, A., Adamu, K., Muhammed, A. I., Labbo, Kabiru. & Sulaiman, A. Impact of Social Studies Education in Tackling Insecurity in Nigeria	32
9	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P09	Usman, Y., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. Insecurity and Gender Disparities in Education: Challenges for Girls' Access to Quality Learning in Nigeria	33
10	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P10	Ibrahim, S., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. Access, Equity and Quality of Nomadic Education in The Face of Insecurity in Nigeria	34
11	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P11	Mohammed, M. M., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. Access, Equity and Quality of Sociology of Education to Citizens as a Panacea for Insecurity in Northern Nigeria.	35
12	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P12	Na'ala, Z. I., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. Educational Quality in Times of Crisis: Assessing the effects of Insecurity on Teaching and Learning Standards in Rural areas of Nigeria	36
13	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P13	Bilyaminu, A., Kainuwa, A. & Sule, M. School Closures and Learning Loss: Investigating the Long-Term Effects of Insecurity on Educational Access and Equality	37
14	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P14	Anas, Y., Kainuwa, A. & Dajor, U. The Problem of Banditry Activities on Girl-Child Education in Zamfara-North Educational Zone, Zamfara State Nigeria	38

15	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P15	Muzzammil, I. P. Education in the Phase of Insecurity in Zamfara State, Nigeria	39
16	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P16	Sheu, A. L. & Sule, M. Impact of Insecurity on the Quality of Teaching and Assessment of Civic Education in Secondary Schools in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State, Nigeria	40
17	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P17	Tukur, N., Abdullahi, A., Abbas, S. D. & Osuji, C. N. Assessing the Effects of Armed Banditry on Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Zamfara State	41
18	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P18	Nafiu, N. & Abbas, S. D. Access, Equity, and Quality of Secondary Education Amidst Insecurity in Nigeria.	42
19	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P19	Yahaya, S. & Osuji, C. N. Quality Assurance in Basic Education: Strategies for Mitigating the Impact of Insecurity on Educational Development in Zamfara State.	43
20	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P20	Bature, Z. S. & Abbas, S. D. Perceived Impact of Strategic Planning on School Performance in Areas Affected by Violence in Zamfara State.	44
21	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(A)-P21	Muhammad, M. I. & Halilu, R. Access to Quality Tertiary Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria.	45
GROUP II: EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS (B), FOE LECTURE ROOM 4			
S/N	ABSTRACT CODE	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1	2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P01	Abubakar, H. A. & Abbas, S. D. Effect of school feeding programme on secondary school students' enrollment and attendance in Gusau local government area, Zamfara state.	47
2	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P02	Maidawa, J. H., Abdulmalik, S., Kainuwa, A. & Sheu, L. A. Predictive Analysis of Quality of Students' O-Level Result and Their Academic Achievement at Federal University Gusau.	48
3	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P03	Osuji, C. N., Muhammad, B. N. & Ashiru, A. Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria: The Role of Educational Administrators.	49
4	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P04	Mafara, R. M. & Sule, M. Prospects and Challenges of 21st-Century Girl-Child Education in Insecurity-Prone Areas in Nigeria.	50
5	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P05	Mukhtar, A., Kainuwa, A. & Shehu, S. Social media as a Challenge to Accessing Equity and Quality Education in Nigeria.	51
6	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P06	Shehu, S. A. & Akilu, I. Improving Access to STEM Education for Children of Internally Displaced Persons in Zamfara State, Nigeria: A Call for Policy Action	52
7	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P07	Shu'aibu, A., Muhammad, S., Sheu, A. L. & Olufunmiola, O. A. Assessment of School Safety Strategies and Their Impact on Learning Outcomes in Conflict-Affected Secondary Schools in Nigeria.	53
8	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P08	Osuji, C. N. & Aliyu, H. Enhancing School Safety through Collaborative Partnerships: The Roles of School Administrators, Security Agencies, and the Community in Zamfara State	54

9	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P09	Jibril, A., Abbas, S. D. & Abdulrauf, A. Strengthening School Effectiveness through Safety Measures Amidst Insecurity: Implications for Educational Quality Assurance in Zamfara State, Nigeria	55
10	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P10	Suhaibu, A., Mafara, M. R. & Abbas, S. D. Influence of School Environment on Learners' Academic Performance Amidst Insecurity: A Study of Talata Mafara Local Government Area, Zamfara State.	56
11	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P11	Mafara, M. B., Suleiman, S. & Arah, Z. I. Access, Equity and Quality of Arts and Social Science Education in the face of insecurity in Nigeria.	57
12	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P12	Hassan, H. M. & Osuji, C. Access to Quality Education in the Face of Insecurity: Implications for National Development.	58
13	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P13	Bello, M. & Murtala, G. T. Assessment of Usefulness in Integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy Among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State	59
14	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P14	Salisu, A., Sani, S. H. Muhammad, S. Sheu, A. L. & Jabir, H. M. Security Challenges and Access to Education in Nigeria: An Assessment of Educational Equity and Learning Outcomes in Conflict-Affected Region	60
15	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P15	Shehu, S. A. & Nuradden, A. K. Influence of Security Challenges on Secondary School Students Academic Performance in English Language in Faskari Local Government Area, Katsina-State	61
16	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P16	Nathaniel, O. & Imrana, S. P. Access, Equity and Quality of Basic, Tertiary and Special Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria: Implications on School Administration.	62
17	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P17	Kainuwa, K., Dajor, U. & Garba, A. L. The Role of Schools as Social Institutions	63
18	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P18	Sani, S. H., Salisu, A., Muhammad, S., Sheu, A. L. & Olufunmilola, O. A. Schooling in the Face of Insecurity: Evaluating the Impact of Armed Conflicts on Learning in Northern Nigeria	64
19	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P19	Musa, Y. T., Kainuwa, A. & Suleiman, S. G. Role of University Education for National Security and Economic Empowerment in Nigeria	65
20	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P20	Yahaya, M. N., Abbas S. D. & Mafara, R. M. The Effects of Insecurity on School supervision: Challenges and Prospects for Enhancing Educational Quality in Nigeria.	66
21	2025-FOEC-ABS- EDU(B)-P21	Osuji, C. N. & Attahiru, A. The Role of Educational Administrators and Parents in Facilitating Access to Quality Education Amidst Insecurity in Zamfara State, Nigeria	67

GROUP III: SCIENCE EDUCATION (A), FOE LECTURE ROOM 3

S/N	AUTHORS	TITLE	PAGE NO.
1	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P01	Adamu, U., Bashir, S., Nuhu, I. L. & Ibrahim, G. L. Impact of Brainstorming Instructional Strategy on Science-Process	69

		Skills for Qualitative Biology Education among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria	
2	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P02	Idris, A., Muhammad, S. A. & Muhammad Z. H. Effects of Flipped Classroom Learning on Academic Achievement and Interest of Secondary School Biology Students in Kano State.	70
3	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P03	Babalola, V. T., Lawal, N. I., Omagwu, A. & Obeda, G. Examining the moderating effect of gender on mnemonics strategy in enhancing the quality of electrochemistry concepts' learning amidst Nigerian insecurity.	71
4	2025-FOEC- ABS-SED(A)-P04	Yahaya, H. Access to Quality Tertiary Education in The Face of Insecurity	72
5	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P05	Olatunbosun, M. L. Assessing the Impact on Insecurity on Access and Quality of STEM Education in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria	73
6	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P06	Nuhu, I. L., Omagwu, A Babalola, V. T. & Obeda, G. Access to Quality Education Amid Insecurity: Evaluating the Middle Basic Science Curriculum in Universal Basic Education Schools in Benue State Nigeria.	74
7	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P07	Umar, S. G., Nuhu, I. L. & Yakubu, A. A. Effect of Jigsaw Instructional Strategy on Performance in Mechanics Concept among Secondary School Physics Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria	75
8	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P08	Yakubu, M. M., Nuhu, I. L. & Yakubu, A. A. Effect of Video-Aid- Simulation Using Hook's Model on Performance in Human Circulatory System among Secondary School Students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State.	76
9	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P09	Sulaiman, A., Ibrahim, A., Ibrahim, M., Aliyu, M. & Abdulwahab, A. Impacts of Social Media on the Academic Achievement of Education Biology Undergraduate Students at Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria.	77
10	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P10	Shuaibu, A. H., Nuhu, I. L. & Salau, A. I. Effects of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Academic Performance in Concept Diffusion among Secondary School Biology Students in Zamfara State	78
11	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P11	Sadiq, Y., Umar, S. & Adamu, U. Qualitative Physics Education: A Survey of the Availability of Qualified Physics Teachers among Secondary Schools in Gusau, Zamfara State	79
12	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P12	Umar, M., Nuhu, I. L. & Yahaya, H. Effects of Computer-Assisted Instruction Strategy using ADDIE Model on Anxiety and Performance in Cell Biology among Senior Secondary Schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria	80
13	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(A)-P13	Sirajo. I., Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. Assessing the Influence of Motor-Generator Device Based Instruction on Students' Motivation in Energy among North-West Colleges of Education, Nigeria.	81
GROUP IV: SCIENCE EDUCATION (B), FOE LECTURE ROOM 3			
S/N	AUTHORS	TITLE	PAGE NO.

1	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P01	Aliyu, K., Sodangi, U. & Usman, A. M. Effect of Flipped-Classroom Strategy Using Van Hiele’s Model on Interest in Geometry Among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State	83
2	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P02	Sani, A., Suleiman, B. & Sule, A. Effect of Problem-Based Strategy on Performance in Algebra for Qualitative Mathematics Education Among Pupils in Zamfara State	84
3	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P03	Muhammad, N., Umar, S. & Yahaya, H. Effects of STAD Strategy on Student’s Performance in Digestion Among Senior Secondary Schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria	85
4	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B) -P04	Ahmad, A. A., Nuhu, I. L. & Yahaya H. Effect of Audio-Visual Aids Using Bransford and Steins Model on Interest and Performance in Cell Division among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State	86
5	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P05	Walidu, D. & Akilu, I. Survey on the Menace of Out-of-School Children on Insecurity and Access to STEM Education and in Zamfara State	87
6	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P06	Jafar, M. B. & Yakubu, A. A. Effect of Jigsaw (IV) Cooperative Strategy on Performance in Organic Chemistry Concept among Secondary School Students in Akko Education Zone Gombe State, Nigeria	88
7	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P07	Abdullahi, M., Umar, S. Nasir, S. Impact of Computer-Laboratory-Simulation Using VARK model on Self – Efficacy and Performance in Titration among senior secondary school students in Zamfara State, Nigeria.	89
8	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P08	Abdulmalik, L. Nuhu, I. L. & Yakubu, A. A. Effects of Three-Pair-Share Strategy Using VARK Model on Performance and Retention in Electrolysis Among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria.	90
9	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P09	Bilyaminu, A., Nuhu, I. L. & Yakubu, A. A. Qualitative Physics Education: Effect of Scaffolding Teaching Strategy on Secondary School Students' Performance in Heat Energy Concept in Zamfara State, Nigeria	91
10	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P10	Yahaya, S. U., Umar, S. & Yakubu, A. A. Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy on Performance in Thermodynamics Concept among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State”	92
11	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P11	Hussaini, M., Bashir, S. Yakubu, A. A. Correlation between Advanced-Organizers-Strategy and Critical-Thinking-skills on Performance in Electrolysis among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria	93
12	2025-FOEC-ABS-SED(B)-P12	Agbo, M. E., Bashir, S. & Brunnoh, I. A. Effect of Scaffolding Strategy using 70:20:10 Model on Performance in Genetics among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State.	94
VIRTUAL PRESENTATION: FACULTY OF EDUCATION BOARD ROOM			
S/N	AUTHORS	TITLE	PAGE NO.

1	2025-FOEC-ABS-V01	Iniobong, M. E. & Azikiwe, W. C. Providing Early Childhood Education to Abandoned Children in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria	96
2	2025-FOEC-ABS-V02	Musa, U., Abdulkadir, H. & Haliru, S. A. Leveraging Artificial Intelligence to overcome Educational Challenges in insecure Regions of Nigeria	97
3	2025-FOEC-ABS-V03	Isaac, B. F., Muhammad, B. & Chado, A. M. Assessment of Secondary School Science Teachers' Intention Towards Entrepreneurship Education in Minna Metropolis, Niger State.	98
4	2025-FOEC-ABS-V04	Obiunu, J., Ekedama, K. Comparative Analysis of Psychological Outcomes Between Students in Conflict-Affected and Secure Regions in Delta State, Nigeria	99
5	2025-FOEC-ABS-V05	Samuel, I. R. & Oka, U. A. Ensuring Inclusive and High-Quality STEM Education amidst Security Challenges in Nigeria	100
6	2025-FOEC-ABS-V06	Tahir, A. A. & Ado, A. B. Evaluating Nigerian Universities' Teacher Education Programs Using the CIPP Model amidst Security Challenges	101
7	2025-FOEC-ABS-V07	Oderhohwo, A. J. Access, Equity and Quality of Guidance and Counselling Education in the Face of Insecurity	102
8	2025-FOEC-ABS-V08	Sunday, A. T. The Role of Technology in Enhancing STEM Education Access and Quality in Insecure Zones in Oyo State	103
9	2025-FOEC-ABS-V09	Duruh, L. C. Administrating Children's Spiritual Development in Early Childhood Care and Education Amidst Insecurity in Nigeria	104
10	2025-FOEC-ABS-V10	Abubakar, K. M. & Ihiosota, C. J. E. Access, Equity and Quality of Early Childhood Education in The Face of Insecurity in Northwest Nigeria	105
11	2025-FOEC-ABS-V11	Danladi, A. Quality of Educational Guidance and Counseling in The Face of Insecurity In Gusau Zamfara State	106

PHYSICAL PRESENTATION

GROUP ONE: EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS (A)

VENUE: FACULTY OF EDUCATION LECTURE ROOM 1

CHAIRMAN: DR. SHEU LUKMAN ADARAMAJA

RAPPATOIR: DR. DAHIRU ABBAS

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P01

Access, Equity and Quality Basic Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria

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Abstract

Access, equity and quality basic education are fundamental human right, essential for personal development, economic growth and social cohesion. However, insecurity in Nigeria poses significant challenges to achieving these goals. The paper itemized insecurity challenges to access, equity and quality basic education. Insecurity has led to the schools' closure in the affected areas denying children access to basic education. The insecurity has displaced millions of people including school going children who are forced to flee their homes and schools. The insecurity creates a climate of fear making it difficult for children to attend school. Insecurity exacerbates existing inequalities in access to education with marginalized communities disproportionately affected. The paper highlight how insecure schools often lack basic resources such as textbooks, furniture and qualified teachers, basic infrastructure like classrooms, libraries and sanitation facilities these and others can compromise the quality of basic education. Conclusion was drawn and possible recommendations were proffered for the way forward, some among others are; government and community should prioritize safety and security to ensure schools are safe and secure with adequate protection for students and teachers. Government should improve access to education to implement programs to increase access to basic education such as mobile schools, online learning platforms and community - based education initiatives. Promote equity and inclusion to implement policies and programs to promote equity and inclusion such as scholarships for marginalized students and teacher training programs

Keywords: Access, Equity, Quality, Basic Education and Insecurity

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P02

Impacts of Insecurity on the Secondary Schools Administration in Birnin Gwari Education Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the impacts of insecurity on the secondary school's administration in Birnin Gwari Education Zone, Kaduna State, Nigeria. Secondary data were used to support the issues raised in the article. The data were source from print materials and online publications by recognized authors and institutions. This paper identified among others impacts of insecurity on the secondary school's administration in Birnin Gwari Education Zone, Kaduna State as: closure /relocation of schools, decline in students enrolment, school girls and women targeted for sexual violence, military use of schools disrupts students' education. The paper also identified that, the insecurity in the zone has a political and economic based as once elections are close, that the frequency of violence attacks and kidnapping were always being reduced and also when it is period of farm harvest the frequency of violence attacks and kidnapping for ransom is almost high. In order to address the challenges of insecurity on secondary schools administration in Birnin Gwari Education Zone, the paper recommended that; government should have political will to fight all forms of insecurity in the zone through security agents and provision of security awareness in the schools through relevant stakeholders including political, religious and community leaders, youths, etc.to serve as a support system for existing security and private organizations to support children education in Birnin Gwari Education Zone, Kaduna State through funding and donations.

Keywords: Impacts, Insecurity, Secondary Schools, Administration

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P03

Insecurity and Educational Inequality: Challenges to Quality Learning in Conflict Affected Regions of Nigeria

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Abstract

This research article examines the dual challenges of insecurity and educational inequality in Nigeria, focusing on their impact on the quality of education. The study highlights how violent conflicts, including terrorism and banditry, particularly in northern Nigeria, disrupt education, leading to school closures, teacher displacement, and the displacement of students. These security challenges exacerbate educational disparities between regions, especially in the northern parts, where economic hardship, gender-based violence, and inadequate government policies compound the crisis. Nigeria's conflict zones see a marked decline in educational access, particularly for girls, who are disproportionately affected by abductions and early marriage. The article further explores how weak infrastructure, underfunding of education, and a lack of targeted government interventions hinder efforts to provide quality learning in these areas. The research suggests that insecurity in Nigeria undermines the country's human capital development, which is crucial for economic growth. In response, the article proposes potential solutions, including mobile schools for displaced children, rebuilding educational infrastructure, gender-sensitive policies, and enhanced teacher training to address the specific needs of students affected by conflict. These solutions aim to mitigate the adverse effects of insecurity and provide equitable access to quality education for all Nigerian children, particularly in conflict-affected regions.

Keywords: Insecurity, Educational Inequality, Challenges, Quality Learning, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P04

Adoption Challenges of the Nigeria Learning Passport Digital Learning Platform Among Upper Basic Education Teachers in Insecurity-Prone Regions of Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

The adoption of digital learning platforms has gained increasing attention in Nigeria, particularly in insecurity-prone regions where access to quality education is severely affected. This study examines the adoption challenges of the Nigeria Learning Passport (NLP) among upper basic school teachers in such regions, identifying key barriers and exploring mitigation strategies. Using a qualitative research approach and snowball sampling technique, data were collected through semi-structured interviews with teachers who have engaged with the NLP. Findings reveal that challenges such as inadequate digital literacy, poor internet connectivity, lack of access to digital devices, and inconsistent government support hinder the effective utilization of the platform. Additionally, socio-economic factors and security concerns exacerbate these challenges, further limiting teachers' ability to integrate NLP into their instructional practices. Despite these obstacles, participants acknowledged the potential of NLP to enhance digital learning and improve educational access if properly implemented. The study recommends targeted teacher training programs, improved internet infrastructure, provision of subsidized digital devices, and strengthened policy frameworks to facilitate the seamless adoption of NLP.

Keywords: Nigeria Learning Passport, digital learning, online education, teacher adoption, insecurity, barriers, mitigation strategies

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P05

**Exploring Access, Equity, and Quality in Early Childhood Education in Nigeria
Amidst In-Security Challenges**

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Abstract

The paper provides an in-depth analysis of the challenges and mitigating factors regarding access, equity, and quality in Early Childhood Education (ECE) in Nigeria amidst ongoing security challenges. The country has faced severe security threats, particularly from Boko Haram insurgency in the northeast and armed banditry in the northwest, significantly disrupting educational services. As ECE is fundamental for cognitive, social, and emotional development, its disruption exacerbates existing inequalities, particularly for children in conflict zones. This paper explained the consequential impact of insecurity on children's access to education, the widening gaps in educational equity, and the deteriorating quality of education in these regions. Similarly, unveiled the trauma caused by violence and displacement which further affects children's emotional well-being, impedes their ability to engage in learning. Additionally, the paper also proposes a range of solutions in order to improve on early childhood access and its equity and these including; Mobile schools, Community-Based initiatives, Digital learning, Teacher support, Psychosocial interventions, Collaborative partnerships, and Increased investment in educational infrastructure. Lastly, recommendations were made on the needs for a comprehensive framework to augments the impact of the insecurity on ECE which invariably would go a long way to promote the right to quality education for all Nigerian children, regardless of their circumstances and where they are living

Keywords: Early Childhood Education, Exploring, Access, Equity, Quality & Insecurity

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P06

Impact of Insecurity on Educational Access and Social Mobility In Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examines the impact of insecurity on educational access and social mobility in Nigeria, focusing on the destabilizing effects of terrorism, banditry, and communal conflicts, especially in northern regions. Insecurity has disrupted educational systems, leading to a decline in school enrollment, academic interruptions, and the destruction of educational infrastructure. Additionally, the psychological toll of living under constant threat has negatively impacted student performance and well-being. The research highlights how insecurity hampers social mobility by limiting access to education, which is a critical determinant of economic advancement. The cyclical nature of insecurity reinforces poverty, as displaced families and communities are unable to provide adequate education for their children, further entrenching socio-economic disparities. Gender disparities are particularly pronounced, with female students being more vulnerable to abductions and gender-based violence. The study employs the Human Security Theory to analyze how insecurity impacts individuals' ability to access education, move freely, and achieve upward social mobility. The findings suggest that addressing the educational challenges posed by insecurity requires a multifaceted approach, including enhanced security, digital learning solutions, and targeted government policies to ensure education remains accessible even in conflict zones. This research calls for increased international collaboration and comprehensive support systems to mitigate the effects of insecurity on education and mobility in Nigeria.

Key Words: Impact, Insecurity, Educational Access, Nigeria, Social Mobility

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P07
**The Role of Government and Community Interventions in Addressing Educational Barriers Amid
the Era of Insecurity in Nigeria**

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Abstract

The persistent insecurity in Nigeria, characterized by insurgency, banditry, and kidnappings, has significantly disrupted the education sector, particularly in conflict-affected regions. Educational activities have been severely impacted by the closure of schools, displacement of students and teachers, and declines in enrollment rates. While the Nigerian government has made efforts through initiatives like the Safe Schools Initiative (SSI) and Universal Basic Education (UBE) policy, challenges such as inconsistent implementation, inadequate funding, and poor infrastructure continue to undermine these efforts. On the other hand, community-based interventions, including local security networks, non-governmental organizations, and faith-based groups, have emerged as complementary responses, providing alternative learning centers, psychosocial support, and advocacy for safer educational environments. This research examines the interplay between government policies and community interventions in addressing the educational barriers exacerbated by insecurity in Nigeria. It highlights the need for a collaborative, multi-stakeholder approach involving government agencies, local communities, and international organizations to sustain educational resilience. The study emphasizes that while government interventions offer a structural framework, community-driven solutions provide localized, adaptive responses, ultimately ensuring more inclusive and uninterrupted access to education in conflict-prone areas.

Keywords: Insecurity, Education, Government, Community Interventions, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P08
Impact of Social Studies Education in Tackling Insecurity in Nigeria

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Abstract

Social Studies Education has been a potent subject that can be used to tackle insecurity in Nigeria. The thrust of this study is to investigate the impact of Social Studies Education in tackling insecurity in Nigeria. The study employed Descriptive survey design. The Total population of 250 upper basic schools Social Studies Teachers across four local government of Zamfara state was selected which include: Gusau, Bangudu, Maru, and Tsafe area. Convenient sampling technique was adopted, the sample size of 152 respondents was employed, the research instrument Questionnaire” Tittle Impact of Social Studies Education in Tackling Insecurity (ISSETIQ)” was employed. to sample the opinion of Social Studies teachers, the questionnaire was validated by two expert from the faculty of education federal university Gusau and had face and content validity. A reliability index of .706 was obtained. Data obtained was analyzed using frequency, percentages, mean and standard deviation of descriptive statistics. the findings revealed that, poor leadership, corruption, marginalization, unemployment and poverty are the causes of insecurity in Nigeria. The study indicated that, students were not attending schools, there was reduction in student’s enrollment in schools, and teachers were not in schools due to insecurity. The study concluded that, Social Studies Education has an impact in tackling insecurity in Nigeria. Thus, recommended that, Social Studies education should be teach to instill values such as honesty, contentment, self-reliant cooperation, tolerance, selflessness, togetherness, patriotism, and unity. this would help greatly in refinement of the mind there by in tackling insecurity. Good and exemplary leadership should be provided, severe punishment should be applied to the corrupt leaders, an inclusive government should be provided, government should create employment opportunities, government should create a safe an enabling environment, government should recruit more security personnel and give them good training to combat insecurity so as students would have access, equal and quality education in Nigeria without being denied there right to education.

Keywords: Impact, Social Studies Education, Insecurity, Upper Basic Schools.

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P09

Insecurity and Gender Disparities in Education: Challenges for Girls' Access to Quality Learning in Nigeria

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Abstract

Insecurity and gender disparities remain significant barriers to girls' access to quality education in Nigeria. Armed conflicts, insurgency, and widespread violence have led to school closures, mass kidnappings, and displacement, disproportionately affecting female students. Socio-cultural norms further exacerbate these challenges, reinforcing traditional biases against girls' education. This study examines how insecurity limits girls' educational opportunities and explores the role of social capital in mitigating these effects. Using Social Capital Theory as a framework, the research highlights the importance of community networks, advocacy groups, and policy interventions in promoting safe and inclusive learning environments. Findings suggest that while initiatives like the Safe Schools Initiative (SSI) offer some relief, a more comprehensive, multi-stakeholder approach is necessary to ensure sustained progress. Strengthening community engagement, investing in alternative education models, and implementing gender-responsive policies are essential for bridging the gender gap in education. Addressing these challenges requires coordinated efforts from the government, civil society, and international organizations to safeguard educational institutions and promote long-term gender equity in learning.

Keywords: Insecurity in Education, Gender Disparities, Girls' Education Social Capital Theory, Conflict-Affected Education

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P10

Access, Equity and Quality of Nomadic Education in The Face of Insecurity in Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper explored the nomadic education and the incidences of herdsmen attacks and national security issues in Nigeria and the way forward. The Fulani are the largest semi-nomadic group in Nigeria. Over the years, they herd their animals across vast areas in search of food which frequently leads to conflicts and clashes with local farming communities in different parts of Nigeria. The conflicts have posed national security challenges in Nigeria. The paper examined the Challenges in the Implementation of Nomadic Education Programme and the roles of Nomadic Education in tackling Insecurity in Nigeria. The paper recommended that the nomadic education should be repositioned for effective delivery. It was also suggested that the three tiers of governments should come together to critically examine the conflicts between the nomads and host communities in order to take decisive measures for improved national security. Based on the findings, the paper recommended among others that Government at all levels, nomads, host communities and international organizations should address this issue of continuous clashes in order to find lasting strategies to overcome the challenges so as to avoid the consequences on national security, ethnic, political, religious and food security in Nigeria. Making the nomadic education functional and accessible, sensitizing the nomads on the need for formal education; resolving disputes between the nomads and host communities early enough and the establishment of ranches and grazing areas as well as the passage of anti-grazing laws by the various governments in Nigeria.

Key words: Nomads, Nomadic Education, Insecurity in Nigeria.

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P11

Access, Equity and Quality of Sociology of Education to Citizens as a Panacea for Insecurity in Northern Nigeria.

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Abstract

This study examined the access, equity and quality of sociology of education to citizens as a panacea for insecurity in northern Nigeria. However, in Northern Nigeria, persistent challenges related to access, equity, and quality of education have exacerbated insecurity, leading to insurgency, banditry, and violent extremism. This study explores how the sociology of education examining the interplay between education and society can serve as a panacea for insecurity in the region. Applying Human Security Theory, the research underscores the role of education in mitigating social inequalities, fostering economic empowerment, and promoting civic engagement. Key barriers such as poverty, cultural norms, inadequate infrastructure, and policy deficiencies hinder educational access and equity, particularly for marginalized groups such as girls and rural populations. The study argues that improving educational opportunities, integrating peace education, and enhancing vocational training can disrupt cycles of poverty and radicalization, reducing security threats. Recommendations include increasing government investment in education, reforming the curriculum to incorporate civic and conflict resolution education, and fostering partnerships between educational institutions, religious leaders, and security agencies. Strengthening educational policies and ensuring inclusive, high-quality education can serve as a long-term strategy for peace and stability in Northern Nigeria.

Keywords: Education and Security, Sociology of Education, Access and Equity in Education, Northern Nigeria Insecurity, Human Security Theory

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU-P12(A)

Educational Quality in Times of Crisis: Assessing the effects of Insecurity on Teaching and Learning Standards in Rural areas of Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined Educational Quality in Times of Crisis: Assessing the Effects of Insecurity on Teaching and Learning Standards in Rural Areas of Nigeria. Insecurity poses a significant threat to educational quality, particularly in rural areas of Nigeria, where terrorism, banditry, and communal conflicts have disrupted teaching and learning. This study assesses the impact of insecurity on educational standards, focusing on school closures, teacher shortages, student displacement, and declining academic performance. Using a mixed-methods approach, data were collected from educators, students, and policymakers through surveys and interviews. Findings reveal that insecurity has led to increased dropout rates, poor teacher retention, psychological trauma among learners, and inadequate learning resources. Theoretical analysis through structural functionalism highlights how these disruptions create systemic imbalances, weakening education's role in social stability and national development. The study recommends strengthening school security, adopting alternative learning models such as digital education, implementing trauma-informed teaching, and fostering community involvement in school governance. Without urgent interventions, insecurity will continue to widen the educational gap between urban and rural areas, further marginalizing vulnerable populations and hindering national progress.

Keywords: Assessing, Insecurity, Educational Quality, Rural Nigeria, Teaching and Learning

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P13

School Closures and Learning Loss: Investigating the Long-Term Effects of Insecurity on Educational Access and Equality

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Abstract

This study examines the long-term effects of school closures due to insecurity on educational access and equality, using Human Capital Theory as a framework. Findings reveal that terrorism, banditry, and communal violence have led to widespread school shutdowns, depriving millions of children of formal education. Prolonged closures result in significant learning loss, declining literacy rates, and increased dropout rates, disproportionately affecting marginalized groups, especially girls. Insecurity also exacerbates teacher shortages, weakens school infrastructure, and widens socio-economic disparities. The study highlights the psychological impact of violence on students and educators, leading to trauma, anxiety, and diminished cognitive performance. It also links school closures to rising insecurity, as out-of-school children face higher risks of criminal recruitment, child marriage, and economic hardship. Addressing these challenges requires improved school security, digital and community-based learning alternatives, teacher training in crisis management, and targeted policy interventions. Without urgent action, educational inequality will worsen, hindering workforce development and economic growth. This research emphasizes the need for coordinated efforts among governments, international organizations, and local communities to protect education and ensure inclusive learning opportunities for all children, even in conflict-affected areas.

Keywords: Insecurity, school closures, learning loss, educational access, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P14

**The Problem of Banditry Activities on Girl-Child Education in Zamfara-North Educational Zone,
Zamfara State Nigeria**

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Abstract

Banditry activities have ravaged Zamfara State, particularly the North Educational Zone, with devastating effects on girl-child education. This study examines the problems of banditry activities on girl-child education in Zamfara North Educational Zone. Banditry has affected almost all aspects of human endeavor, including Girl-Child Education in Northern Nigeria. This study examined the effects of insurgency/Banditry on Girl-Child Education in the Zamfara North Educational Zone. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study collected data from 200 respondents, including girls, parents, teachers, and community leaders. The findings reveal that banditry activities have led to widespread destruction of schools, abduction of girls, and displacement of communities, thereby disrupting their educational pursuits. The study identifies fear, anxiety, and psychological trauma as major problems faced by girls in accessing education. Additionally, cultural and socio-economic factors exacerbate the vulnerability of girls to banditry-related disruptions. Four (4) community schools selected across the most affected LGAs in Zamfara North Educational Zone in Zamfara state, namely: Kaura Namoda, Zurmi, Shinkafi and Birnin-Magaji LGAs. The research recommends that the government, policymakers, and other stakeholders should prioritize the safety and security of schools, provide psychosocial support to affected girls, and implement policies that promote girl-child education in conflict-affected areas.

Keywords: Banditry, Girl-Child Education, Zamfara North Educational Zone, Conflict, Displacement, Abduction.

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P15

Education in the Phase of Insecurity in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper presented the impact of insecurity on educational sector particularly in Zamfara state of Nigeria, specifically, seeks to analyse the effect of educational setback in Zamfara State. Moreover, the paper presented that insecurity has affected development of education in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The paper identified; reduction in education funding, unstable academic calendar, reduction in education manpower, led to students' death and reduction in students' enrolment, retention and completion. Based on this finding, the paper hereby recommends that; Government should deploy personnel from various educational institutions to help in security management. Government should address the factors responsible for various forms of insecurity in order to devise a lasting solution to the problem. Government should address the high level of unemployment. Government should pay serious attention to the security of the borders against both external and internal criminals. Government should strengthen prosecution and legal actions on banditry to ensure perpetrators of offenses such as bandits, terrorism and kidnappers are brought to justice. Finally, the paper relied in secondary data collected for analysis.

Keywords: Education, Insecurity, Zamfara State, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P16

**Impact of Insecurity on the Quality of Teaching and
Assessment of Civic Education in Secondary Schools in Gusau Educational Zone, Zamfara State,
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Abstract

This study examines the impact of insecurity on the quality of teaching and assessment of civic education in secondary schools in Gusau educational zone, Zamfara state, Nigeria. The research explores how persistent security threats such as banditry, kidnappings, and school attacks affect teachers' effectiveness, student engagement, and assessment practices in Civic Education. Utilizing a survey research design. The population of the study comprised all the 156 civic education teachers in the study area. A multi-stage sampling technique was used to select 108 Civic Education teachers for the study. A validated structured questionnaire was used in the study. Cronbach's alpha reliability coefficient of 0.83 was derived to satisfied the internal consistency of the instrument. Findings indicates that insecurity significantly disrupts Civic Education teaching, leading to reduced instructional time, lower teacher motivation, and decreased student participation. Additionally, assessment and evaluation of students are negatively impacted, with delays in examinations, limited assessment diversity, and reduced teacher confidence in evaluating students. The study concludes that insecurity poses a severe threat to the quality of Civic Education, potentially weakening students' understanding of civic responsibilities and national identity. The study recommends enhanced security measures in schools, psychological support for teachers and students, and policy interventions on assessment practice for quality teaching and assessment of Civic Education despite prevailing security challenges.

Keywords: Assessment, Civic Education, Insecurity, Quality Teaching, Teachers Engagement

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P17

Assessing the Effects of Armed Banditry on Effective Administration of Public Secondary Schools in Zamfara State

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Abstract

Armed banditry has become a critical threat to the effective administration of public secondary schools in Zamfara State, disrupting not only the learning process but also the overall governance and management of schools. The persistent insecurity has led to the displacement of students and teachers, destruction of school infrastructure, and a decline in the quality of education. This paper examines the multidimensional effects of armed banditry on school administration, focusing on how insecurity has weakened leadership structures, impeded instructional supervision, and hindered effective decision-making processes. The study highlights the increasing difficulty faced by school administrators in enforcing policies, maintaining discipline, and ensuring the safety of staff and students. Additionally, the constant fear of attacks has led to high levels of teacher absenteeism, student dropouts, and a general decline in morale among education stakeholders. The findings of this paper underscore the urgent need for strategic interventions by government authorities, security agencies, and educational policymakers to mitigate the adverse effects of armed banditry on the school system. Strengthening security in schools, providing psychosocial support for affected individuals, and ensuring adequate funding for educational institutions are critical steps toward restoring administrative efficiency and educational stability. The implications of this study are profound for stakeholders in the education sector, including policymakers, school administrators, teachers, and community leaders. It calls for a more proactive approach in addressing security concerns, reinforcing resilience in school administration, and ensuring that education remains accessible and effective despite prevailing security challenges.

Keywords: Effects, Armed Banditry, School Administration, Public Secondary Schools

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P18

Access, Equity, and Quality of Secondary Education Amidst Insecurity in Nigeria.

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Abstract

This paper examines the critical role of access, equity, and quality in secondary education as essential tools for addressing Nigeria's pervasive insecurity. It highlights the objectives of secondary education, analyzes the security situation in Nigeria, identifies the root causes of insecurity, and discusses its effects on the education sector. The paper argues that secondary education can foster security development by equipping students with the knowledge, skills, and values needed to address societal challenges. It proposes practical solutions, including curriculum reform, teacher training, increased funding, community involvement, and the integration of technology. The paper concludes that prioritizing access, equity, and quality in secondary education is vital for achieving sustainable security and development in Nigeria.

Keywords: Secondary Education, Insecurity, Access, Equity, Quality, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P19

Quality Assurance in Basic Education: Strategies for Mitigating the Impact of Insecurity on Educational Development in Zamfara State

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Abstract

Quality assurance in basic education is essential for ensuring access, equity, and sustainable educational development, particularly in regions affected by insecurity. In Zamfara State, ongoing security challenges such as armed conflicts, school abductions, and community displacement have severely disrupted the education sector. These challenges have led to declining teaching and learning standards, reduced teacher motivation, and a general loss of confidence in the school system. Addressing these issues requires a strong quality assurance framework that ensures continuity, resilience, and effectiveness in educational delivery. This paper explores strategic approaches for mitigating the impact of insecurity on basic education through quality assurance mechanisms. Emphasis is placed on strengthening school leadership, fostering teacher commitment, enhancing school monitoring and evaluation, and promoting community participation in school governance. By drawing from existing literature and best practices, this paper contributes to ongoing discourse on safeguarding educational access and quality in conflict-prone regions. It provides a roadmap for ensuring that despite insecurity, the foundational goals of basic education—equity, quality, and sustainability—are not compromised. The findings of this paper have significant implications for stakeholders in educational management. Policymakers will benefit from insights on designing more adaptive and security-conscious educational policies. School administrators and headteachers will gain strategies to improve institutional resilience and maintain teaching effectiveness in crisis situations. Teachers will find recommendations on professional support systems that enhance motivation and retention in challenging environments. Additionally, community engagement strategies discussed in this paper can help foster local ownership and support for schools, thereby strengthening educational stability in Zamfara State.

Keywords: Quality Assurance, Basic Education, Educational Development, Insecurity

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P20

Perceived Impact of Strategic Planning on School Performance in Areas Affected by Violence in Zamfara State

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Abstract

Strategic planning is a critical management tool for enhancing school performance, particularly in conflict-affected regions where educational institutions face persistent instability, resource limitations, and disruptions to teaching and learning. This paper examines the perceived impact of strategic planning on school performance in violence affected areas in Zamfara State, emphasizing its role in fostering institutional effectiveness, and sustainable educational development. It explores how structured planning frameworks contribute to goal clarity, efficient resource allocation, and adaptive leadership, enabling schools to navigate the complexities of volatile environments. The discussion highlights key dimensions of strategic planning, including stakeholder engagement, contingency planning, and long-term developmental strategies, which collectively enhance school governance, teacher effectiveness, and student learning outcomes. Findings suggest that schools with well-articulated strategic plans are better equipped to mitigate the adverse effects of insecurity, maintain operational stability, and sustain quality education despite external threats. Furthermore, effective strategic planning fosters collaboration among educational stakeholders, including government agencies, school leaders, and local communities, in developing practical solutions to the challenges posed by conflict. The paper underscores the need for policymakers and education administrators to integrate strategic planning into governance structures, ensuring that schools in conflict-prone areas adopt proactive, flexible, and inclusive approaches to educational management. By embedding strategic foresight into policy frameworks, educational institutions can enhance their resilience and contribute to broader efforts aimed at safeguarding education in violence-affected areas in Zamfara State.

Keywords: Strategic Planning, School Performance, Violence-Affected Areas, Educational Development

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(A)-P21

Access to Quality Tertiary Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria

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Abstract

For the past two decades, there seems to be a steady growth in the number of tertiary institutions, both public and private, in Nigeria. This may be due to the rapid increase in the country's population and the high demand for access to higher education. With constant political interference in the administration of Nigerian tertiary institutions coupled with insecurity ravaging most parts of the country, the future of access to quality tertiary education in the country does not seem bright. Nigerian society, more than ever before, has been experiencing insecurity of different kinds, which are capable of destroying not only the educational landscape of the nation but the entire security architecture of the country. The continuous disruption to education by frequent school attacks has caused millions of children to significantly miss out on learning skills they would have acquired if they had been in the classroom. In order to confront this problem better, there is a need for pragmatic approach to tackle the problem from its bud. It is against this backdrop that this paper discussed the issues of access to quality Tertiary education in the face of insecurity in Nigeria. It unraveled the challenges of access to quality tertiary education in the face of insecurity in Nigeria and put forward suggestions for the improvements.

Keywords: Access, Tertiary Education, Insecurity

PHYSICAL PRESENTATION

GROUP TWO: EDUCATIONAL FOUNDATIONS (B)

VENUE: FACULTY OF EDUCATION LECTURE ROOM 4

CHAIRMAN: DR. SHEHU SULEIMAN ABDULLAHI

RAPPATOIR: DR. AHMAD KAINUWA

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P01

Effect of School Feeding Programme on Secondary School Students' Enrollment and Attendance in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara state.

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Abstract

This study was conducted objectively to determine the effect of school feeding program on enrollment and attendance of Secondary Schools students in Gusau local government area, Zamfara State. In order to purposely achieve the objective, one research question was formulated. Descriptive survey research design was adopted. The population of the study comprised all teachers in Secondary Schools in Gusau local government area of Zamfara State. The total number of 50 teachers was selected through stratified sampling technique from five selected Secondary Schools in Gusau metropolis of Zamfara State. A structured questionnaire on four Likert type scale instruments with 10 items was adopted as an instrument for data collection. Reliability was computed using Cronbach alpha methods and obtained a value of 0.8 and above. Mean deviation was used to answer the research questions. The study findings revealed that school feeding programs play a significant role in attracting students to enroll in school, particularly among lower income communities. The provision of daily meals was identified as a key factor in motivating parents to send their children to school and ensuring consistent attendance. Based on the findings, several recommendations are proposed to enhance the impact of school feeding programs on enrollment and attendance: such that school feeding should be a continuous process to support students to have access to quality education. The study concludes that schools and policymakers can further capitalize on the benefits of such programs to promote educational access, retention, attendance, enrollment and academic success among secondary school students.

Keywords: school feeding program, enrollment and attendance

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P02

Predictive Analysis of Quality of Students' O-Level Result and Their Academic Achievement At Federal University Gusau

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Abstract

This study investigates the relationship between O-level results and academic performance, measured by Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA), among students at Federal University Gusau. By employing a stratified random sampling technique, a representative sample of 370 students from various faculties and departments was analyzed. Descriptive and correlational analyses were conducted to explore how O-level grades in key subjects predict university academic performance. The analysis spans the entire university, individual faculties, academic departments, and different levels of study, providing a comprehensive view of the impact of O-level results on academic success. The findings reveal that while there is a weak overall correlation between O-level results and CGPA across the entire university, the relationship varies significantly by faculty and department. Notably, only the Faculty of Management and Social Sciences exhibited a statistically significant correlation, highlighting discrepancies that may be linked to subject-specific or curricular factors. Additionally, longitudinal analysis by academic level indicated minimal correlation between O-level results and CGPA as students' progress through their studies, suggesting that other factors may increasingly influence academic outcomes over time. These findings have implications for admission policies and academic support programs, indicating a need for a more nuanced approach to using O-level results as a predictor of university performance. Recommendations are provided for policy adjustments and targeted interventions that consider faculty-specific requirements and support mechanisms. Further research is suggested to explore additional predictors of academic success, such as socio-economic background and extracurricular engagement, and to extend this analysis across multiple universities for broader applicability.

Keywords: Predictive, O-level Result, Academic Achievement, Federal University Gusau

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P03

Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria: The Role of Educational Administrators

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Abstract

Insecurity has continued to be a great challenge to the education sector in Nigeria. This paper examines the role of educational administration, concept of education, objectives of education, concept of administration, types of administration, concept of educational administration, structure of educational administration, goals of educational administration, challenges of educational administration, functions of educational administration, concept of insecurity, causes of insecurity, implication of insecurity. The paper identified that, educational administrators, were in fear as a result of insecurity and that has affected the school's administration. The paper also revealed that some teachers were not coming to schools and teach due to insecurity which affected the teaching and learning there by reducing access to education. The paper concluded that educational administrators had an influence to tackle insecurity in Nigeria. The paper indicated that poor leadership, corruption, unemployment, marginalization and poverty were the factors responsible for insecurity in Nigeria. Thus, the paper recommended that, adequate security personnel should be recruited and deployed to schools, create employment opportunities, create an enabling environment for business, government should insure that, punishment are served to the corrupt people, government should provide an inclusive government.

Keyword: Education, Role, Educational Administrator.

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P04

Prospects and Challenges of 21st-Century Girl-Child Education in Insecurity-Prone Areas In Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the prospects and challenges of 21st-Century Girl-Child Education in Insecurity-Prone Areas in Nigeria. Girl-child education is a fundamental driver of national development, yet insecurity remains a critical barrier in many parts of Nigeria, particularly in the northern regions. Widespread insurgency, banditry, kidnappings, and communal conflicts have led to school closures, reduced enrollment, and heightened parental fears, disproportionately affecting female students. This study examines both the prospects and challenges of 21st-century girl-child education in insecurity-prone areas of Nigeria, using feminist theory as a framework. The research highlights how gender-based violence, economic hardship, and cultural norms exacerbate educational inequality. Despite these obstacles, initiatives such as digital learning, community engagement, and government interventions offer potential solutions. The study recommends a multi-sectoral approach involving enhanced school security, policy reforms, psychosocial support, and economic empowerment programs to ensure safe and equitable access to education for girls in conflict-affected areas.

Keywords: Girl-Child Education, Insecurity, Feminist Theory, School Safety, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P05

Social Media as a Challenge to Accessing Equity and Quality Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

The Information and Communication Technology ICT era has brought about a widespread adoption of computers, the internet, and mobile phone devices has created a new human sophisticated environment, and which characterized by rapid information exchange, digital connectivity, and e-commerce. This Contemporary era is known as ' Web-based Environment ' (present day time) As mentioned, we are currently living in a web-based environment, where the internet and online platforms have become an integral part of our daily life, commerce, social interactions and Education. Social media has become an integral part of modern in human life and especially their Education, but its impact on education in Nigeria is a subject of concern. This study examines the challenges posed by social media to accessing equity and quality education in Nigeria. A mixed-methods approach was employed, combining survey data from 100 students and 20 educators with in-depth interviews and focus group discussions. The findings reveal that social media addiction, limited access to quality educational resources, and negative impacts on mental health are significant challenges to accessing equity and quality education in Nigeria. The study recommends the implementation of digital literacy programmes, responsible social media use policies, and quality educational resources to mitigate these challenges. The study contributes to the literature on the impact of social media on education and provides insights for policymakers, educators, and practitioners working to promote access to equity and quality education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Social media, education, equity, quality, Nigeria.

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P06

Improving Access to STEM Education for Children of Internally Displaced Persons in Zamfara State, Nigeria: A Call for Policy Action

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Abstract

This position paper explored the urgent need to improve access to STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education for children of internally displaced persons (IDPs) in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Zamfara is one of the states severely affected by ongoing insecurity and displacement in northwest states of Nigeria. The displacement crisis as a result of insecurity in Zamfara created significant barriers to education, with children of IDPs facing numerous challenges such as lack of infrastructure, limited access to educational resources, and disrupted learning environments. In spite these challenges, STEM education remained a factor in the socioeconomic development of individuals and communities as it provides essential skills for future opportunities and self-reliant. The paper also discussed the importance of STEM education for displaced children and argued that it was not only a means for empowerment but also an avenue of ensuring long term stability in conflict affected areas. It reviewed the state of STEM education for IDPs in Zamfara state, identified existing gaps, and assessed the effectiveness of ongoing efforts to improve educational access. The paper then proposed several policy recommendations aimed at overcoming these challenges. In conclusion, the paper called for immediate and sustained policy action to ensure equitable access to quality STEM education for children of IDPs in Zamfara State.

Keywords: Educational Access, STEM Education, Children, Internally Displaced Persons, Policy

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P07

Assessment of School Safety Strategies and Their Impact on Learning Outcomes In Conflict-Affected Secondary Schools In Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper examined the Assessment of School Safety Strategies and Their Impact on Learning Outcomes in Conflict-Affected Secondary Schools in Nigeria. School safety is crucial for effective learning, particularly in conflict-affected regions where insecurity disrupts education. In Nigeria's North-East and North-West, insurgency, banditry, and communal clashes have led to school closures, student displacement, and psychological trauma. This study assesses school safety strategies and their impact on learning outcomes in conflict-affected secondary schools. Using Maslow's Hierarchy of Needs as a theoretical framework, the research explores how physical and non-physical safety measures such as perimeter fencing, security personnel, community engagement, and psychosocial support affect students' academic performance and well-being. The study employs a mixed-methods approach, combining surveys, interviews, and safety audits to evaluate the effectiveness of these interventions. Findings are expected to reveal the extent to which school safety measures enhance student attendance, concentration, and achievement while mitigating the negative effects of conflict. The study contributes to policy discussions on improving educational resilience in conflict zones and achieving Sustainable Development Goal 4

Keywords: Assessment, School Safety, Conflict, Learning Outcomes, Security Strategies

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P08

Enhancing School Safety through Collaborative Partnerships: The Roles of School Administrators, Security Agencies, and the Community in Zamfara State

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Abstract

School safety is a fundamental prerequisite for effective teaching and learning, as it directly influences students' academic performance, teachers' productivity, and overall institutional effectiveness. In Zamfara State, where security challenges pose significant threats to education, enhancing school safety requires a collaborative approach involving school administrators, security agencies, and the broader community. This paper examines the critical roles of these stakeholders in fostering a secure learning environment through coordinated efforts, shared responsibilities, and proactive intervention strategies. School administrators play a pivotal role in implementing safety policies, strengthening internal security measures, and fostering a culture of vigilance among staff and students. Security agencies contribute by providing intelligence, responding to threats, and ensuring a structured security framework within school environments. Meanwhile, community involvement is essential for strengthening neighborhood watch initiatives, engaging in awareness programs, and fostering social responsibility in safeguarding schools. A well-structured partnership among these stakeholders not only mitigates security threats but also promotes trust, transparency, and collective responsibility in protecting educational institutions. The study underscores the necessity of continuous training, policy reinforcement, and resource mobilization to support security initiatives. The findings have significant implications for relevant stakeholders in educational management such as the education policymakers, school leaders, law enforcement agencies, and school-based community, as they emphasize the need for a unified approach to school safety. On this basis, strengthening these collaborative partnerships will ensure a sustainable educational system, thereby fostering a conducive atmosphere for teaching, learning, and overall academic excellence in the State.

Keywords: School safety, collaborative partnerships, school administrators, security agencies, community

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P09

Strengthening School Effectiveness through Safety Measures Amidst Insecurity: Implications for Educational Quality Assurance in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

School effectiveness is a crucial determinant of educational quality and national development. However, the increasing insecurity in Nigeria has posed significant challenges to the safety and functionality of schools, disrupting teaching and learning processes, diminishing student performance, and undermining teachers' commitment. The escalating threats of attacks on schools, abductions, and violence have created an urgent need to strengthen safety measures to safeguard the educational environment and enhance institutional resilience. This paper explores how robust safety measures contribute to improving school effectiveness amid insecurity, with a focus on their implications for educational quality assurance in reference with Zamfara State, northwest Nigeria. Effective safety strategies, such as infrastructural security enhancements, psychological support systems, crisis response mechanisms, and multi-stakeholder collaboration, play a fundamental role in ensuring a conducive learning environment. These measures not only protect lives but also create stability, fostering an atmosphere where teachers can perform effectively and students can achieve optimal learning outcomes. The paper argues that integrating security measures into the broader educational quality assurance framework reinforces institutional accountability, promotes policy adherence, and enhances the overall performance of schools. Furthermore, this study underscores the critical roles of educational stakeholders, including policymakers, school administrators, teachers, parents, and security agencies, in sustaining a secure and effective school system. Strengthening school safety requires proactive interventions, well-defined policies, and strategic partnerships to mitigate the adverse effects of insecurity on education. By prioritizing safety within the quality assurance framework, educational institutions can enhance their effectiveness, ensuring sustainable academic excellence and institutional stability in Zamfara State, Nigeria.

Keywords: School Effectiveness, Safety Measures, Insecurity, Educational Quality Assurance

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P10

Influence of School Environment on Learners' Academic Performance Amidst Insecurity: A Study of Talata Mafara Local Government Area, Zamfara State

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Abstract

The school environment significantly influences learners' academic performance, particularly in regions affected by insecurity. In Talata Mafara Local Government Area, Zamfara State, persistent security threats such as banditry and school attacks have disrupted the education system, leading to instability in school operations, teacher shortages, and psychological distress among students. This study explores how school infrastructure, teacher stability, safety measures, and students' psychological well-being contribute to academic achievement amidst these challenges. A conducive learning environment fosters student engagement, motivation, and overall academic success. However, in crisis-prone areas, factors such as fear, school closures, and inadequate safety mechanisms pose significant barriers to learning. The findings of this study underscore the critical need for proactive measures to improve school security, strengthen teacher support systems, and provide psychological and emotional support to students. Schools must adopt adaptive strategies such as enhanced security frameworks, community involvement, and government interventions to ensure learning continuity. Furthermore, the study highlights the role of educational stakeholders, including policymakers, school administrators, and community leaders, in creating safe and supportive learning environments. This study has far-reaching implications for educational planning and policy formulation. By addressing the challenges posed by insecurity, stakeholders can contribute to improved educational outcomes, resilience-building among learners, and sustainable development in the education sector.

Keywords: School Environment, Learners, Academic Performance, Insecurity

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P11

Access, Equity and Quality of Arts and Social Science Education in the face of insecurity in Nigeria.

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Abstract

The continuing instability in Nigeria has seriously destabilized the educational system, where critical thinking, cultural expression, and civic engagement are essential pillars for national development. The increasing terrorist activities combined with banditry incidents and kidnappings along with violent conflicts threaten both student and educator safety while simultaneously creating barriers that prevent learners in high-risk areas from obtaining quality educational opportunities. Based on Nigeria's current security issues, the study examines institutional and socioeconomic constraints that impede effective learning opportunities and thoroughly evaluates the relationship between access, equity, and quality education. The research employs multidimensional analysis to reveal how insecurity led to educational facilities being closed, student and teacher displacement and blocked students from accessing educational resources and buildings. The research examines how security disruptions create worsened educational disparity between marginalized groups consisting of rural communities and both IDPs and lower-income households. The study reviews how insecurity affects school quality by examining the emotional strain on teaching staff and students together with falling student achievements and exchanges to outdated non-professional learning approaches. This study examines different security-focused policies and local community resilience plans along with institutional countermeasures which aim to reduce the educational adversities stemming from insecurity. The study investigates four essential policy measures which incorporate computer-based learning systems along with security-focused education buildings and expanded counselling services and specify financing programs for vulnerable students. The paper demonstrates how government agencies, civil society organizations, and international bodies work to create an inclusive sustainable educational framework. The findings underscore the urgent need for a holistic, context-specific approach to safeguard and enhance access, equity, and quality in education amid Nigeria's insecurity crisis. The study shows how government institutions collaborate with international organizations and civil society groups to develop an inclusive, sustainable educational environment.

Keywords: Access, Equity, Quality, Arts and Social Science Education, Insecurity, Nigeria, Educational Resilience, Conflict-Affected Learners.

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P12

Access to Quality Education in the Face of Insecurity: Implications for National Development.

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Abstract

Insecurity possess a formidable challenge to accessing quality education in Nigeria, undermining the country's national development aspirations. This study investigates the impact of insecurity on access to quality education, exploring the implications for national development. Using a mixed-methods approach, the study combines quantitative and qualitative data to provide a comprehensive understanding of the relationship between insecurity, education, and national development. The finding of this study reveals that insecurity has a devastating impact on access to quality education. Leading to reduced enrollment rates, increased dropout rates, and diminished educational outcomes. Furthermore, the study highlights the far reaching implications of insecurity for national development, including reduced economic growth, increased poverty, and diminished global competitiveness. The study recommends multi-faceted approach to addressing insecurity and promoting access to quality education, including increased investment in education, improved security measures, and community-based initiatives.

Keywords: Insecurity, Quality Education, National Development, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P13

Assessment of Usefulness in Integration of Technology -Enhanced Strategy Among Colleges of Education Pre-Service Teachers in Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study was on assessment of usefulness in integration of technology enhanced strategy among colleges of education for pre-service teachers in Zamfara state. One specific objective guided the study; the objective was transformed into research question. Descriptive survey design was adopted with a population of 2952 pre-service teachers. The sample size for the study was 333 respondents which were selected using the research Advisor Table. The data Obtained were analyzed using frequencies and percentages to present the bio-data of the respondents while mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. The finding revealed that pre-service teachers perceived the usefulness in integration of technology enhanced strategy among colleges of education. The study recommended that; management of Colleges of Education should provide soft skills courses to improve level of perceived usefulness in integration of technology enhanced strategy among Colleges of Education pre-service teachers.

Keywords: Usefulness, Technology Integration, and pre-service teachers

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P14

Security Challenges and Access to Education in Nigeria: An Assessment of Educational Equity and Learning Outcomes in Conflict-Affected Regions

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Abstract

This study examined the security challenges and access to education in Nigeria: an assessment of educational equity and learning outcomes in conflict-affected regions. Security challenges in Nigeria, including insurgency, banditry, and communal violence, have severely impacted access to education, particularly in conflict-affected regions. These challenges disrupt school attendance, displace students and teachers, and weaken the overall education system, leading to significant disparities in educational equity and learning outcomes. This study assesses the extent to which insecurity affects access to education and evaluates the effectiveness of assessment practices in measuring student performance in these regions. Educators, students, and policymakers to understand the barriers to equitable education. The findings highlight the urgent need for policy interventions, security reforms, and alternative learning strategies to ensure inclusive and resilient education systems despite ongoing security threats.

Keywords: Security Challenges, Access to Education, Educational Equity, Learning Outcomes, Conflict-Affected Regions

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P15

Influence of Security Challenges on Secondary School Students Academic Performance in English Language in Faskari Local Government Area, Katsina-State

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Abstract

This study investigates the prevalence and impact of security challenges on secondary school students, particularly in relation to their attendance and engagement in English language classes. Utilizing a structured questionnaire, the research aims to identify how security issues affect educational experiences and academic performance of students. The findings revealed that a significant majority of students, approximately 66.7%, reported feeling unsafe attending school due to security concerns. Consequently, 66.7% of respondents indicated that security challenges negatively impact their participation in English language classes. Moreover, about 60.8% of students expressed that their academic performance in English language is adversely affected by these challenges. Specifically, 70.8% of students noted difficulties in concentrating on their studies due to security issues, further highlighting the detrimental effects of these concerns on educational outcomes. The study also uncovered a consensus among both students and teachers regarding the negative influence of security challenges on the overall learning environment in English language. Approximately 63.3% of teachers acknowledged that security concerns hinder effective teaching and learning, reinforcing the need for improved safety measures in schools. In conclusion, this research underscores the urgent need for educational institutions to prioritize the safety and well-being of students to enhance their academic experiences. Implementing comprehensive security measures and fostering open communication can significantly improve student engagement and performance in the face of security challenges. The findings suggest that addressing these issues is essential for creating a conducive learning environment in secondary schools.

Keywords: Security Challenges, Secondary School Students, Academic Performance, English Language

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P16

Access, Equity and Quality of Basic, Tertiary and Special Education in the Face of Insecurity in Nigeria: Implications on School Administration

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Abstract

Over the years, Nigerian Educational system has significantly aligned, improved and enabled individuals by providing opportunities for learning and growth through basic, tertiary and special education. However, the emergence and lingering of the bedeviling insecurity in Nigeria, consequentially, has retarded the accessibility, equity and quality of Basic, Tertiary and Special education. Insecurity has plunged Nigeria into tragedies resulting from the activities of terrorism and insurgency, banditry, kidnapping, ethno-religious conflict, farmer-herder clashes, militancy in Niger Delta, organized crime, abductions, food insecurity, and these problems has been causative of internal displacement of staff and students, poor academic performance, teacher shortages, destruction of educational facilities, close of educational institutions, economic hardship among other tragedies. This paper explores how insecurity affects access, equity, and quality in education (Basic, Tertiary and Special), and examines the implications on school administration hence, recommendations to improving on situation based on findings. This paper adopts secondary data (published and unpublished papers) to provide empirical facts concerning highlighted points. The secondary data were sourced from journals online and printed materials. Similarly, the recommendations include: strengthening schools security protection, promoting alternative education, engaging communities, formulation and implementation of developmental policies, addressing the porosity of borders, ensuring the effectiveness of the rule of law against perpetrators irrespective of social or political class.

Key words: Insecurity, Education

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P17

The Role of Schools as Social Institutions

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Abstract

Schools, as fundamental social institutions, play a pivotal role in shaping both individual lives and broader societal structures. This paper, the role of schools as social institutions, explores how educational establishments function beyond mere centers for academic instruction by serving as arenas for socialization, cultural transmission, and the reinforcement or transformation of social norms and values. Drawing on classic sociological theories from Durkheim's insights into the integrative functions of education to Bourdieu's discussions on cultural capital and social reproduction; this paper examines the multifaceted contributions of schools to society. The discussion will highlight the dual role of schools in fostering social cohesion and perpetuating social stratification. On one hand, schools serve as vital environments for social integration, where students learn essential norms, values, and behaviors that enable them to participate effectively in civic life. Through structured curricula, extracurricular activities, and peer interactions, educational institutions inculcate a shared sense of identity and community, thereby contributing to societal stability and continuity. On the other hand, the paper will critically assess how schools can also mirror and reinforce existing social inequalities. Institutional practices, curriculum biases, and differential access to quality education often contribute to the reproduction of class, race, and gender disparities. By examining case studies and empirical research, the paper will discuss the mechanisms through which educational systems may inadvertently limit upward social mobility, despite their potential as sites for transformative change. Furthermore, the paper will explore contemporary challenges and opportunities faced by schools in an increasingly globalized and digital society. Topics such as the impact of technology on social interactions, the evolution of pedagogical practices, and the role of schools in addressing issues like multiculturalism and social justice will be critically analyzed. By integrating theoretical frameworks with practical insights, this paper aims to provide participants with a comprehensive understanding of the complex interplay between education and society. Ultimately, the discussion will illuminate how schools, as enduring social institutions, not only mirror the values and conflicts of their surrounding environments but also possess the potential to act as catalysts for positive social transformation.

Keywords: Education, School, Social institutions, transformative change, society, social stratification

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P18

Schooling in the Face of Insecurity: Evaluating the Impact of Armed Conflicts On Learning In Northern Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluates the impact of insecurity on schooling, focusing on how violent conflicts influence school attendance, learning outcomes, teacher availability, and overall educational infrastructure. The persistent armed conflicts in Northern Nigeria have significantly disrupted the education sector, affecting students' access to quality learning. This paper highlighted the extent of the crisis and its long-term consequences on educational development. Findings highlight the challenges faced by students and educators, including school closures, displacement, psychological trauma, and reduced government interventions. The study concludes with policy recommendations for mitigating these challenges and ensuring the resilience of the education system in conflict-affected regions.

Keywords: Armed Conflict, Insecurity, Education Disruption, Northern Nigeria, Learning Outcomes

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P19

Role of University Education for National Security and Economic Empowerment in Nigeria

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Abstract

University education in Nigeria and indeed any other part of the world plays a crucial role in the supply of highly skilled manpower to manned different sectors of the nation's economy. Security as an essential concept in commonly associated with the alleviation of threats to cherished values, especially the survival of individuals groups or objects in the near future. Thus, national security as the name implies, involves the ability to pursue cherished political and social ambition. This paper examines the role of university education for national security and economic empowerment, security challenges in Nigeria, the objectives of Nigeria's national security policy, university management in Nigeria, challenges facing university education and its products, university education and global economy, the inability of the government to address the root causes of dissatisfaction, anger and agitation among various groups in the country resulted to serious security challenges confronting the contemporary Nigerian state. The conclusion here is that, government can use university education as a tool for national security and economic empowerment. This therefore that, the culture of the true morality as the implementation level of university education should be emphasized on against the current practice of craze for paper qualification citizen education and peace studied should from part of the school curriculum at all levels of education. The emphasis should be a promotion of nationality and heightening of empathy, and finally, universities should be adequately funded by giving top priority in the budget at least 30% of the budget should be allocated to universities.

Keyword: Economic empowerment, national security management, Nigeria, university education

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P20

The Effects of Insecurity on School supervision: Challenges and Prospects for Enhancing Educational Quality in Nigeria.

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Abstract

This paper investigates the effects of insecurity on school supervision in Nigeria, focusing on the obstacles it creates for improving educational quality. It discusses how insecurity, represented by violence, kidnapping, and various threats, hinders effective supervision and negatively influences teacher performance, student attendance, and overall learning results. The study highlights significant challenges that school supervisors encounter in unsafe contexts and suggests actionable strategies to improve supervision methods and create safer learning environments, ultimately aiming to enhance the quality of education in Nigeria.

Keywords: Insecurity, School supervision, Educational Quality, Nigeria

2025-FOEC-ABS-EDU(B)-P21

**The Role of Educational Administrators and Parents in Facilitating Access to Quality Education
Amidst Insecurity in Zamfara State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

The role of educational administrators and parents in ensuring access to quality education amidst the growing insecurity in Zamfara State, Nigeria, is a critical issue that has far-reaching implications for both academic outcomes and the well-being of students. This paper will investigate how educational administrators and parents can collaborate to facilitate uninterrupted access to education in a region beset by various forms of insecurity, including banditry, kidnappings, and violent conflicts. By examining the strategies adopted by school administrators to ensure safety, maintain educational standards, and manage the disruptions caused by insecurity, as well as the role of parents in supporting their children's education under these challenging conditions, this paper will highlight key factors that contribute to educational resilience. The paper will also explore the collaborative efforts between local communities, security agencies, and government bodies to create a safe learning environment. The findings of this paper will underscore the importance of proactive measures, such as community engagement, security collaborations, flexible learning arrangements, and the provision of psychological support for students. This study aims to offer practical recommendations for improving the educational landscape in Zamfara State and other conflict-prone regions in Nigeria.

Keywords: Educational Administrators, Quality Education, Insecurity,

PHYSICAL PRESENTATION

GROUP THREE: SCIENCE EDUCATION (A)

VENUE: FACULTY OF EDUCATION LECTURE ROOM 3

CHAIRMAN: DR. NUHU ISHAQ LAWAL

RAPPATOIR: DR. GANIYU ADEDO

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P01

Impact of Brainstorming Instructional Strategy on Science-Process Skills for Qualitative Biology Education among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the impact of brainstorming instructional strategy on science-process skills in biology among secondary school students in Zamfara state, Nigeria. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study which adopted the Quasi-Experimental design of the pretest, posttest non-randomized control group type. The target population of the study was a total of 25,335 (16,395 male; 8,940 female) SS2 students while the sample was 115 (62 Male; 53 Female) students. Multi-stage sampling was used in selecting 2 schools for the study. The experimental group was exposed to brainstorming instructional strategy, whereas the control group was taught using conventional method for a period of 4 weeks. Cellular Respiration was the biological concept treated while Science-Process Skills Inventory (SPSI) was the research instrument used for data collection. Three experts validated the SPSI and its reliability index was 0.82 using test-retest method and Cronbach Alpha tool. The data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation and One-Way ANCOVA statistical tools at 0.05 significant level. The result of the study revealed that the experimental group students had higher science-process skills than those in the control group. It was also found that there was no significant gender interaction effect on science-process skills of the students exposed to the strategy. Thus, it was concluded that the strategy enhances students' science-process skills and is gender-friendly. It was therefore recommended that secondary school biology teachers should adequately adopt the strategy so as to improve students' acquisition and utilization of science-process skills, academic performance and ways of doing science.

Keywords: Brainstorming, Strategy, Science-Process Skills, Biology

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P02

Effects of Flipped Classroom Learning on Academic Achievement and Interest of Secondary School Biology Students in Kano State.

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Abstract

The study investigated the effects Flipped Classroom Learning on the Academic Achievement and Interest of Secondary School Biology Students in Kano State Nigeria. Three objectives, three research questions and three hypotheses were formulated to guide the study. The study employed quasi-experimental research design, specifically pre-test, post-test nonequivalent control group design to guide the study. The population of the study consists of all science and technical schools' students (SS2) offering biology, totaling five thousand one hundred and forty-four (5144) in Kano State. The sample size of the study comprises of two hundred and eighty (280) SS2 Biology students which include one hundred and eighty-nine (189) female and ninety-one (91) male students randomly selected from six secondary schools in Kano State. Biology Achievement Test (BAT) and Biology Students Interest Questionnaire (BSIQ) were used as the instrument for data collection in the study. The reliability index of BAT using Cronbach alpha was found to be 0.96 while for the BSIQ was found to be 0.89. Mean and Standard Deviation were used in answering the research questions, while ANCOVA statistical technique was used in testing the research hypotheses. The result of the study reveals improvement on the mean academic achievement and interest on biology students taught the concept of ecology via flipped classroom learning. However, the study reveals a significant gender difference between the academic achievement of male and female students in favor of the female students' when exposed to flipped classroom learning. It was recommended that; biology teachers should strive to use flipped classroom learning in teaching their students.

Keywords: flipped classroom learning, interest, biology, academic achievement

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P03

Examining the Moderating Effect of Gender on Mnemonics Strategy in enhancing the Quality of Electrochemistry Concepts' learning amidst Nigerian Insecurity.

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Abstract

This study examines the moderating role of gender on Mnemonics Strategy in Enhancing the Quality of Electrochemistry concepts learning in terms of students' academic achievement, retention and perception amidst Nigerian Insecurity: Focusing on science secondary schools, Kano-Nigeria. Non-equivalent Quasi-experimental research design was engaged for the study. The study sample consists of the 270-students (141-girls & 129-boys) present in the four selected intact classes. The subjects were divided into Experimental Group (EG) and Control Groups (CG). The EG was taught using Mnemonics Strategies while the CG was taught with the conventional Lecture Method (CLM). Two instruments of data collection used in the study are; Electrochemistry Achievement Test (EAT) and Students' Perception of Electrochemistry Questionnaires (SPEQ) with the reliability indices of 0.99 and 0.93 respectively. Mean, Standard deviation, Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) and Mann Whitney u-test were the statistical tools used for data analyses. The results revealed a non-statistically significant gender difference in academic achievement, knowledge retention and perception shift of students in electrochemistry concepts. The study recommends among others, the use of Mnemonics strategy in the preparation of learning resources for chemistry and in the teaching of electrochemistry concepts to enhance knowledge retention, students' perception and academic achievement in Chemistry as a whole.

Keywords: Gender; Mnemonics Strategy; Academic Achievement; Knowledge Retention, Students' perception; Electrochemistry Concepts.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P04

Access to Quality Tertiary Education in The Face of Insecurity

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Abstract

Insecurity poses a significant threat to access to quality tertiary education, disrupting the learning process and undermining academic outcomes which has negatively impacted the quality of tertiary education thereby creating fear in schools, shortage of teachers, increasing the rate of school drop-outs leads to poor academic performance, kidnapping of pupils, students and teachers, occupying school buildings, closure of schools among others. In order to reduce the impacts of insecurity and access to quality education, This article examined Access to Quality Tertiary Education In The Face of Insecurity, it highlight the Access to Nigerian education system; quality and equity Nigerian education; challenges faced by students, educators and institutions, underscores the need for proactive measures to ensure the safety and security of tertiary education environments, and to provide innovative solutions that support access to quality education amidst insecurity

Keywords: Access, Quality Tertiary Education, Insecurity

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P05

Assessing the Impact on Insecurity on Access and Quality of STEM Education in Gusau Local Government Area, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the impact of insecurity on access and quality of STEM education in urban and rural areas of Gusau Local Government, Zamfara State. A survey of 100 teachers from urban and rural schools was selected. The research design of this study was descriptive survey, the study was guided by two objectives, two research questions and one hypothesis was formulated which was tested at 0.05 level of significance. Data was collected from the sample using a questionnaire. The questionnaire was validated and pilot tested, a reliability of 0.75 was obtained using Cronbach alpha. The data collected was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics. The results show significant difference in access to STEM resources between urban and rural schools. Insecurity was found to have negative impact on quality of STEM education. The study recommends the state government to address all issues causing insecurity in Zamfara state as a whole in order to allow equal accessibility to STEM education for all students irrespective of their location.

Keywords: STEM education, insecurity, access, quality

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P06

Access to Quality Education Amid Insecurity: Evaluating the Middle Basic Science Curriculum in Universal Basic Education Schools in Benue State Nigeria

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Abstract

This study evaluates the implementation of the Middle Basic Science Programme within Universal Basic Education (UBE) schools in Benue State, Nigeria. It focuses on two key areas: the qualifications of Basic Science teachers and the availability and utilization of instructional materials. A survey research design was employed, gathering data through structured questionnaires administered to Basic Science teachers across urban and rural schools in Benue State. The study utilized descriptive statistics and hypothesis testing to analyze the collected data. Findings reveal a significant shortage of qualified science teachers, with only a small percentage meeting the necessary requirements, while the majority lack specialized training. Additionally, the study highlights a severe lack of instructional materials, particularly in rural schools, which hampers effective science teaching and learning. The under-utilization of available resources further compounds these challenges. The research concludes that improving teacher qualifications through targeted recruitment and professional development, alongside better resource provision and utilization, is critical for enhancing Basic Science education in Benue State.

Keywords: Basic Science, Universal Basic Education, Teacher Qualifications, Instructional Materials, Science Education, Benue State, Nigeria, Curriculum Implementation.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P07

Effect of Jigsaw Instructional Strategy on Performance in Mechanics Concept among Secondary School Physics Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates the effects of jigsaw instructional strategy on performance in mechanics concept among secondary School Physics students in in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design, specifically, the pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design in which intact classes were assigned to the experimental and control groups. A sample size of 120 (67 male and 53 female) physics students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The experimental group were taught mechanics concept using jigsaw instructional strategy while the control group were taught using lecture method. Mechanics Concept Test (MPT) instrument was used in the collection of data. Three experts validated the instrument and its reliability index was 0.82 using test-retest method. The data collected were analyzed using mean, standard deviation to answer the research questions and one-way Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypothesis at 0.05 significant level. The results obtained revealed that the experimental group students had higher performance than those in the control group. It was also found that there was no significant gender interaction on the students exposed to jig-saw strategy. Thus, it was concluded that the strategy enhances students' performance and its gender-friendly. It was therefore recommended that physics teachers should adopt Jigsaw instructional strategy to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

Keyword: Jigsaw, Instructional Strategy, Mechanics Concept, Physics

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P08

Effect of Video-Aid- Simulation Using Hook's Model on Performance in Human Circulatory System among Secondary School Students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of video-aid-simulated exploring hook's model on academic performance in human circulatory system among secondary school students in Gusau Metropolis, Zamfara State. Quasi experimental pre-test, post-test non randomized control group design was adopted for the study. The target population was all Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Biology during the 2024/2025 academic session in Zamfara State. The sample size for the study was 317 students using Multistage sampling (cluster, purposive and simple random) technique. An instrument named Biology Performance Test on Human Circulatory System (BPTHCS) was employed for data collection. The reliability of the instrument was determined using test-retest method and reliability coefficient of 0.84 was obtained which shows that the instrument is reliable. Two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and two null hypotheses were tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Result of the study reveals that, students taught Human Circulatory System using video-aid-simulation had better performance than those exposed to lecture method and has no gender influence. Hence, gender friendly. It was therefore, concluded that the use of video-aid-simulation is more effective in improving students' academic performance than lecture method. Thus, therefore recommend that, Science teachers should integrate the use of video-aid-simulation in the classrooms especially when teaching difficult abstract concepts.

Keywords: Video-aid-simulation, Hook's model, academic performance and Human Circulatory System.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P09

Impacts of Social Media on the Academic Achievement of Education Biology Undergraduate Students at Federal University Gusau, Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

Social media's global reach is undeniable, permeating all segments of society, including students. This study examined the impact of social media usage on the academic achievement of Education Biology undergraduates at Federal University Gusau. By utilizing a survey research design, a self-administered questionnaire was distributed to 217 students across 200 to 400 levels Undergraduates. Spearman's correlation analysis was employed to explore the relationship between social media usage and academic achievement with Cumulative Grade Point Average (CGPA) serving as the achievement indicator. The findings suggest that social media usage detrimentally affects academic achievement, primarily through distractions during study sessions and lectures with many students exhibiting signs of social media addiction. Based on these results, the study recommends the implementation of an orientation program for incoming students to educate them about the potential academic impacts of social media and strategies for its effective use in supporting their studies.

Keywords: Biology Education, Achievement, undergraduate Students

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P10

Effects of Laboratory Instructional Strategy on Academic Performance in Concept Diffusion among Secondary School Biology Students in Zamfara State

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of laboratory strategy on academic performance in concept Diffusion among secondary school Biology students. Two research questions and two hypotheses guided the study. The non-randomized control group, pretest-posttest quasi experimental design adopted for the study. A sample of 250 senior secondary II biology students from six secondary schools in Gusau Educational Zone was drawn from a population of all students and 20 schools using purposive sampling technique. The instrument used for data collection was the Biology Academic Performance Test (BAT) which yielded a reliability coefficient of 0.71. The data collected were analyzed using mean and standard deviations to answer the research questions while t-test was used to test the hypotheses at 0.05 level of significance. The findings revealed that there was significant difference in the mean academic performance scores ($p = 0.00 < 0.05$) of students taught Biology concepts using investigative laboratory instructional strategy and those taught using expository method, in favour of the laboratory strategy group. In terms of gender, there was no significant difference between the mean academic performance scores ($P = 0.21 > 0.05$) of male and female students taught using investigative laboratory strategy. Based on the findings, it was concluded that the use of investigative laboratory instructional strategy enhanced students' academic performance in Biology than the expository method. It was further recommended that Biology teachers should use investigative laboratory instructional strategy in teaching Biology which provides students with an opportunity to carry out practical activities by themselves thereby enhancing their academic performance.

Keyword; Laboratory, Instructional Strategy, Academic performance, Diffusion

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P11

Qualitative Physics Education: A Survey of the Availability of Qualified Physics Teachers among Secondary Schools in Gusau, Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigated the availability of qualified physics teachers among senior secondary schools in Gusau, Zamfara state, Nigeria. The target total population of the study comprised of all physics teachers in the public senior secondary schools within Gusau local government of Zamfara state. A sample of thirty-six (36) physics teachers was randomly selected from the thirty-three senior secondary schools in the local government. Three research questions were raised to guide the study using descriptive survey design. Questionnaire on Availability of Qualified Physics Teachers (QAQPT) was used for data collection. A descriptive statistic was used to answer research questions using simple percentage and range. The results revealed that there are available physics teachers among senior secondary schools in the local government, but not all of them are qualified to teach physics because they did not have adequate teaching professional background. Teachers did not graduate with a degree in physics education. The study concluded that teachers' qualifications and experiences promote students' academic performance and their attitude towards physics. It was therefore recommended that governments should employ adequate physics teachers and learning materials to encourage students to have positive attitude towards physics and only those qualified should be given the nod to teach physics in our senior secondary schools.

Keywords: Availability, Qualified Physics Teachers, Performance

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P12

Effects of Computer-Assisted Instruction Strategy using ADDIE Model on Anxiety and Performance in Cell Biology among Senior Secondary Schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to examine the effect of Computer-Assisted instruction strategy using ADDIE model on anxiety and performance in cell biology among senior secondary schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Quasi-experimental pretest posttest control group research design was adopted for this study. The population of this study consist of all senior secondary two (SS II) in Zamfara state and sample of 130 students from an intact class of four public schools were selected. Three research questions were posed and three null hypotheses formulated to guide the study. The two instruments used was cell biology performance test (CBPT) and cell biology state trait anxiety inventory questionnaire (CBSTAIQ) for data collection, 30 multiple choice objectives type was used and were all validated by experts in science education, Biological Science and measurement and evaluation from federal University Gusau. The instrument was pilot tested with thirty SSII biology Students that are not part the sample of the study. Test-retest method was used to determine the reliability coefficient of the instrument and Pearson's Product Moment-Correlation Coefficient was used to compute the reliability coefficient, which was found to be 0.74. The experimental groups were exposed to cell Biology concept lesson with Computer Assisted Instruction strategy using ADDIE model for the period of six weeks while the control group were taught cell Biology lesson with lecture method. Data collected was analyzed using the Statistical Package for the Social Science (SPSS) in accordance with the research objectives of the study. The hypotheses were tested using ANCOVA at $p < 0.05$ level of significance. The results obtained from the analyses showed that there were significant differences between the mean scores of the experimental and control groups in performance. The findings revealed that the computer-assisted instruction strategy using ADDIE model in the experimental group performed better than the control group using conventional method of Discussion, Demonstration and questioning and no significance difference between the performance and anxiety of male and female students. Therefore, it was recommended that Government, policy makers, stakeholders, curriculum planners and developers, organizations and parents should assist in designing training and exposing both the teachers and students be engaged in an active process of learning such as hands-on, learning discoveries in a systematic order which are some of the principles of model so that they create and discover the real world base on the effect of computer-assisted instruction strategy using ADDIE model by organizing, conference, seminar and workshop.

Key words: Effect, computer-assisted instruction strategy, ADDIE model, anxiety, performance and cell Biology.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(A)-P13

Assessing the Influence of Motor-Generator Device Based Instruction on Students' Motivation in Energy among North-West Colleges of Education, Nigeria

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Abstract

This research work investigated the influence of Fabricated Motor Generator Device based instructions on students Motivation, in Energy among colleges of education students in North-West, Nigeria. The study adopted quasi – experimental research design. The population of the study comprised of all N.C.E 1 students of 2024/2025 academic session. The sample was made up of 100 N.C.E.1 student of colleges of Education from North-West geopolitical zone, Nigeria. Two research questions were answered in the study. The research instrument used was Motivation psychometric test adopted from Bin Dayel,2018 for data collection with little modification. Motivation psychometric test was validated by three experts to obtain a reliability coefficient of 0.85 using test retest reliability method. Mean and standard deviation was used to answer the research questions. Result obtained from the study revealed that students that were taught Energy Concepts using fabricated Motor-Generator Device based instructions are motivated higher than those taught using lecture method with a mean gain of 8.26 against 6.73 and female students are highly motivated with mean gain of 8.73 than the male students with mean gain of 7.94. In conclusion, therefore science teachers are advised to use Motor-Generator Device based instruction in teaching Energy concepts in colleges of educations. Finally, is was recommended that lecturers in colleges of Education should expose their students to Motor-Generator based instructions and that male students should be given more attention as female students are motivated higher than male students.

Keywords; Fabricated Motor Generator Device, Motivation, Energy Concept

PHYSICAL PRESENTATION

GROUP FOUR: SCIENCE EDUCATION (B)

VENUE: FACULTY OF EDUCATION LECTURE ROOM 2

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2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P01

Effect of Flipped-Classroom Strategy Using Van Hiele's Model on Interest in Geometry Among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State

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Abstract

Mathematics education, particularly geometry, often struggles to capture students' interest due to traditional lecture-based teaching methods that emphasize memorization over understanding. This study explores how the Flipped-Classroom Strategy (FCS) using Van Hiele's Model can make learning more engaging for secondary school students in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Using a quasi-experimental design, the study compares two groups: one experiencing flipped learning with Van Hiele's Model and another taught through conventional methods. To measure students' enthusiasm, motivation, and attitude toward geometry, the Geometry Interest Inventory (GII) is used before and after the intervention. Early results indicate that students exposed to the flipped-classroom approach show greater interest and engagement in geometry than their peers in the traditional setting. The flipped approach, which encourages peer collaboration, active exploration, and deeper conceptual understanding, appears to create a more stimulating learning environment. Based on these findings, the study advocates for the integration of flipped learning strategies into mathematics education, alongside ongoing teacher training to maximize its impact. Future research will examine whether this boost in interest also leads to better long-term performance and retention in geometry.

Keywords: Flipped-Classroom Strategy, Van Hiele's Model, Geometry Interest, Active Learning, Mathematics Education.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P02

Effect of Problem-Based Strategy on Performance in Algebra for Qualitative Mathematics Education Among Pupils in Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigated the effect of a problem-based learning (PBL) strategy on the performance of algebra among lower basic education pupils in Zamfara State, Nigeria. The research addressed the persistent issue of poor mathematics performance rates among pupils, which has been attributed to traditional lecture-based teaching methods that fail to engage students actively in deep conceptual understanding. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design, specifically the Pretest-Posttest Non-equivalent Control Group Design, to compare the outcomes of pupils taught using PBL with those exposed to conventional lecture methods. The sample consists of primary 1-3 pupils, selected through purposive and multi-stage sampling techniques. Data collection involves administering pre- and post-tests, as well as a reshuffled algebra Performance Test (APT). Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) were used to analyze the data at a 0.05 significance level. The study aims to determine the mean performance of pupils taught with PBL, as well as any gender-based differences in performance. The findings were expected to provide insights into the effectiveness of PBL in enhancing mathematical proficiency, offering a viable alternative to traditional teaching methods in lower basic education. The research instruments were validated by the experts in Science Education and Mathematics, and reliability is established using Pearson products moment correlation coefficient (PPMC). Data analysis was conducted using SPSS version 23.0. The study contributed to the growing body of evidence supporting constructivist approaches in mathematics education, emphasizing active learning, critical thinking, and real-world application.

Keywords: Problem-based learning, Performance, Algebra, Lower basic education.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P03

Effects of STAD Strategy on Student's Performance in Digestion Among Senior Secondary Schools in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined the effect of Student Team Achievement Division (STAD) strategy on student's performance in digestion among senior secondary schools in Zamfara state, Nigeria. A pre-test, post-test control quasi experimental research design was employed for the study. A sample size of 122 SSII was selected. The sample size was sampled using simple random sampling technique. Two intact classes were used for experimental and control groups. The experimental group was taught using Student Team Achievement Division (STAD) strategy while the control group was taught using conventional method. A validated research instrument, Biology Performance Test (BPT) for data collection with reliability coefficient of 0.71 was used. Mean and Standard Deviation were used to answer the research questions. The result revealed that significance difference existed between the performance of students taught using STAD and those taught using conventional methods in indicating the effects of treatment using STAD strategy. The researchers recommended that teachers and curriculum planners should include the use of STAD strategy in the curriculum for teaching Biology and digestion in particular.

Keywords: *STAD, Performance, Digestion*

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P04

Effect of Audio-Visual Aids Using Bransford and Steins Model on Interest and Performance In Cell Division among Senior Secondary School Students In Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigates the effect of audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model on interest and performance in cell division among senior secondary school students in Zamfara state. Three research questions were raised and three null hypotheses were tested. The study adopted quasi-experimental design involving pre-test and post-test. The total population of the study was 72,577 (42,728 male; 24849 female) senior secondary school students for the 2024/2025 session in all the 189 senior secondary schools in Zamfara state while the target population was twenty-five thousand three hundred and thirty-five (25, 335) SSII biology students. The population of male students were sixteen thousand three hundred and ninety-five (16,395) and the remaining eight thousand nine hundred and forty (8,940) were females. A sample of one hundred and twenty (120) students from an intact class from senior secondary two (SS II) of public schools were selected for this study. The researcher uses audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model as treatment for the experimental group while control group were exposed to discussion method. The instrument used for data collection was cell division performance test (CDPT) and Cell division interest scale questionnaire (CDISQ). A 30 multiple choice objective type performance test covering the five phases of cell division was used. Reliability co-efficient of 0.82 was obtained using Kuder-Richardson (K-R 21). Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) was used to analyze the hypotheses. The findings revealed that the experimental group performed better than the control group. There was no significant difference in the performance of males and female students. The experimental group retained better than the control group while there was no significant difference in interest in male and female students in the experimental group. It was recommended that teachers should be exposed to the use of audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model, organize workshops and seminars and symposia on audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model to assist teachers deliver lessons to enhance learning among students generally.

Keywords: Audio-visual aids using bransford and steins model, Interest, Performance, Cell Division.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P05

**Survey on the Menace of Out-of-School Children on Insecurity and Access to STEM Education
and in Zamfara State**

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Abstract

The increasing number of out-of-school children in Zamfara State posed a serious threat to access to STEM education, with insecurity being a major contributing factor. This study employed a survey research design to examine the causes of school dropouts, the extent to which insecurity affected access to STEM education, and the specific educational needs of out-of-school children. A structured questionnaire was used as research instruments to collect data. The population consisted of out-of-school children, parents, teachers, and school administrators, with a sample size of 300 respondents selected using a stratified and purposive sampling technique. Data were collected through questionnaire administered by face-to-face survey. The data were analyzed using descriptive statistics (percentages, mean scores). The findings of the study revealed that insecurity, poverty, and cultural barriers significantly hindered access to STEM education. The study recommended improving school security, expanding scholarship programmes, and implementing flexible learning models such as digital and community-based education to ensure long-term development in Zamfara State.

Keywords: Out-of-School Children, Access, STEM Education, Insecurity,

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P06

Effect of Jigsaw (IV) Cooperative Strategy on Performance in Organic Chemistry Concept among Secondary School Students in Akko Education Zone Gombe State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The purpose of this study was to investigate the effect of Jigsaw-IV Cooperative Learning technique on performance in organic chemistry concepts. Quasi-experimental research design specifically pretest post-test non randomized control group design was adopted for the study. Two objectives with corresponding research questions and null hypothesis, respectively guided the study. Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two chemistry students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Akko Educational Zone, Gombe state. Chemistry Achievement Test (CAT) was used to measure performance for the study, The instrument was validated by three experts and reliability index of 0.80 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research question and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. Result revealed that there was a significant difference between performance of students taught inorganic chemistry concepts using jigsaw cooperative instructional strategy and those exposed to lecture method. Further, a non-significant difference result on gender was obtained. Thus, gender friendly. Base on the finding It was concluded that Jig-Saw strategy improves students' performance and further recommended that the use of Jig-Saw (IV) strategy should be encouraged among chemistry teachers

Keywords: Jigsaw (IV) Strategy, Performance, inorganic Chemistry

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P07

Impact of Computer-Laboratory-Simulation Using VARK model on Self – Efficacy and Performance in Titration among senior secondary school students in Zamfara state, Nigeria

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Abstract

This paper investigates the impact of computer – laboratory – simulation using VARK model on self – efficacy and performance in titration among senior secondary school students. This study was conducted in Zamfara state Nigeria. Quasi experimental design was Adopted for the study using pretest – posttest. Two schools were purposively selected. One school was used as experimental group and one school as control group. The population of the study comprised all (25,335) twenty-five thousand three hundred and thirty-five chemistry students from 189 Government senior secondary schools in Zamfara. A sample of 150 students were randomly selected which comprised 82 male and 69 female participants. The instruments used for collecting data was chemistry performance test (CPT) and computer – laboratory – simulation titration self – efficacy questionnaire (CLSTSEQ), the instrument was validated by experts with the reliability coefficient of 0.83 using Cronbach Alpha. The data was collected using ANCOVA TO test the hypotheses. two research question and two hypotheses were used. there is no significant impact in mean score between the male and female students taught titration using computer – laboratory – simulation and those taught with traditional method. This implies that computer simulation is very essential in titration and it will provide opportunity for students to have capability in improving their performance in practical especially titration. Based on the findings, it was recommended that Government and other stakeholders should support and encourage STEM education using technology and simulation.

Keyword: Computer laboratory simulation, self-efficacy and performance, titration.

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P08

Effects of Three-Pair-Share Strategy Using VARK Model on Performance and Retention In Electrolysis Among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study assessed the Effect of Three-Pair-Share Strategy on Academic Performance and Retention in Electrolysis of Senior Secondary Schools two (SS2), Students. The study adopted a quasi- experimental research design the population was 25,335 from 189 public schools SS2 students offering chemistry in Zamfara State. A sample of 70 students drawn from 2 schools was selected using multi- stage sampling techniques. One instrument was used for data collection namely Electrolysis Performance Test (EPT). The instrument was duly validated by experts and have reliability coefficient of 0.87 using Test-retest method, two research questions and two null hypotheses guided the study. One of the research questions: What is the mean performance score of student taught electrolysis using three pair strategy and those taught same concept using conventional lecture method? Descriptive statistics of mean was used to answer the research questions while standard deviation was adopted to a certain the homogeneity or other wise of the respondent's performance scores. Inferential statistics of analysis of covariance (ANCOVA) was used to test the formulated hypotheses at 0.05 alpha level. Finding of the study revealed that three pair strategy significantly enhanced performance and retention scores of SS2 students in electrolysis more than conventional lecture method. Base of this finding the study recommended amongst others that the Zamfara state ministry of education should organized seminars, workshops and conferences for teachers most especially chemistry teachers on how to uses three-pair-Share strategy in teaching electrolysis.

keywords: electrolysis, academic performance, retention, three pair strategy

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P09

Qualitative Physics Education: Effect of Scaffolding Teaching Strategy on Secondary School Students' Performance in Heat Energy Concept in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study investigated the effect of scaffolding strategy on performance in heat energy among senior secondary school students in Zamfara state. The study adopted a quasi-experimental design where pre-test, post-test non randomized control group was employed. The target population of the study was a total of 25,335(16,395 male & 8,940 females) ss2 students while the sample size used was 120 (67 male & 53 female) students that offer Physics in senior secondary schools in the two educational zones of Gusau and Kaura-Namoda of Zamfara state. Multistage sampling technique was used to select 2 schools for the study. The experimental group was exposed to scaffolding strategy while the control group was taught via conventional lecture method. Heat energy performance test (HEPT) and students' motivation questionnaire (SMQ) was employed as the research instruments for the study. Two experts from science education department and one expert from Physics department validated the instruments with 0.82 as the reliability index using Cronbach Alpha method. The data collected was analyzed through mean, standard deviation and one-way (ANCOVA) statistical tools at 0.05 level of significance. The result of the study revealed that, the experimental group students performed better than those of the control group. Also, the research findings revealed that, there was no significant gender interaction effect on the students' performance hence, it is a gender friendly strategy. However, it was recommended that, Physics teachers should adopt the scaffolding strategy as it enhances student's performance in Physics so as to strive qualitative learning outcome.

Keywords: Scaffolding, Performance, Heat Energy, Physics Education

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P10

Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy on Performance in Thermodynamics Concept among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State”

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Abstract

This study investigates the Impact of Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy on Performance in Thermodynamics Concept among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State. Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted quasi-experimental research design, specifically, the pretest-posttest non-equivalent control group design using an intact class. A sample size of 140 (77 male and 63 female) chemistry students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The experimental group were taught Thermodynamics concept using Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy while the control group were taught using lecture method. Chemistry Performance Test (CPT) instrument was used for study. The CPT was validated by experts and reliability index of 0.75 was obtained using Cronbach alpha reliability test. Descriptive statistics was used to answer the research question and analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 level of significance. The results obtained revealed that there is significant difference between performance of students taught thermodynamics using Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy and those taught using lecture method. It was also revealed that there was no significant gender interaction effect on the students exposed to Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy. Thus, it was concluded that the strategy enhances students' performance and its gender-friendly. It was therefore recommended that Chemistry teachers should adopt Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy to improve teaching and learning outcomes.

Keyword: Artificial-Intelligence-Enhanced strategy, Performance, Thermodynamics, Chemistry

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P11

Correlation between Advanced-Organizers-Strategy and Critical-Thinking-skills on Performance in Electrolysis among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study investigates Correlation between Advanced-Organizers strategy and Critical-Thinking-Skills on Performance in Electrolysis among Secondary School Chemistry Students in Zamfara State, Nigeria Two research questions and corresponding hypotheses guided the study. The study adopted correlation research design, using an intact class. Population of the study consists of all senior secondary school class two chemistry students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Zamfara State. A sample size of 120 (67 male and 53 female) Chemistry students were selected from the target population using multi-stage sampling technique. The experimental group were taught electrolysis concept using Advanced-Organizers strategy and Critical-Thinking-Skills while the control group were taught using lecture method. Electrolysis Performance Test (EPT) was explored for the study. The EPT was validated by experts and its reliability index obtained was 0.82 using Cronbach alpha reliability. The data collected were analyzed using descriptive statistics to answer the research questions and Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient (PPMC) to test the null hypothesis at 0.05 significant level. The results obtained revealed that there is a significantly positive relationship between Advanced-Organizers strategy and Critical-Thinking-Skills on Performance in electrolysis concept among secondary school chemistry students in Zamfara State, Nigeria. Base on the finding it was concluded that Advanced-Organizers-Strategy influences critical-thinking skills for improved performance in Chemistry among Secondary School Students in Zamfara State. It was further recommended that Chemistry Teachers should explore the advanced-Organizers-strategy to improve Critical-Thinking-Skills during teaching and learning to improve performance in Chemistry.

Keyword: Advanced-Organizers -Strategy, Critical-Thinking-Skills, Performance, Electrolysis

2025-FOE-ABS-SED(B)-P12

Effect of Scaffolding Strategy using 70:20:10 Model on Performance in Genetics among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State

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Abstract

This study investigated the Effect of Scaffolding Strategy using 70:20:10 Model on Performance in Genetics among Senior Secondary School Students in Zamfara State. Quasi experimental research design, specifically pre-test, post-test non randomized control group design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of all Senior Secondary School class two (SSII) Biology students during the 2024/2025 academic session in Zamfara State. The sample size for the study was 210 students using Multistage sampling technique. Biology Performance Test was used to collect data for the study. BPT was validated by experts and reliability index of 0.85 was obtained using test-retest method. Two research questions were answered using mean and standard deviation and corresponding hypotheses tested using Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) at 0.05 level of significance. Result of the study reveals that, there is a significant difference between performance of students taught Genetics using Scaffolding strategy and those exposed to lecture teaching method. Furthermore, no significant interaction effect with gender. Hence, scaffolding strategy is gender friendly. It was therefore, concluded that the use of scaffolding strategy is more effective in improving students' academic performance than lecture method. Thus, therefore recommends that, Biology teachers should integrate the use of Scaffolding strategy during teaching and learning of biology.

Keywords: Scaffolding Strategy, Performance Genetics

VIRTUAL PRESENTATION

VENUE: FACULTY OF EDUCATION BOARD ROOM

CHAIRMAN: DR. ABUBAKAR SADIQ HARUNA

RAPPATOIR: DR. YAKUBU A. ABDULLAHI

FOE-2025-ABS-V01

Providing Early Childhood Education to Abandoned Children in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The situation of abandoned children in Akwa Ibom State, Nigeria, highlights the urgent need for comprehensive early childhood education initiatives designed to address their unique challenges. These children, frequently lacking familial support and educational opportunities, experience significant cognitive, emotional, and social disadvantages. This continues the pattern of poverty, social isolation, and discrimination. This study examines the provision of early childhood education for abandoned children, focusing on identifying gaps, barriers, and potential pathways for transformative interventions. A mixed-methods approach was used to collect data through surveys, focus group discussions, and interviews with key stakeholders, including caregivers, educators, social workers, and policymakers. The findings highlight systemic inadequacies, such as underfunded educational programs, a lack of specialized training for teachers, societal stigma, and fragmented policy frameworks that do not adequately address the unique needs of abandoned children. The research also highlights the transformative potential of inclusive and well-structured ECE programs in fostering holistic development, improving educational outcomes, and breaking cycles of disadvantage. Recommendations include the establishment of dedicated ECE centres, increased funding, community-based support systems, and the integration of psychological and social care into educational frameworks. This study contributes to the growing body of knowledge on the intersection of education and child welfare in Nigeria, emphasizing the urgency of creating equitable opportunities for abandoned children. By advocating for systemic reforms and community collaboration, the research charts a pathway toward ensuring that every child, regardless of their background, can access the foundational education they need to thrive.

FOE-2025-ABS-V02

Leveraging Artificial Intelligence to overcome Educational Challenges in insecure Regions of Nigeria

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Abstract

Armed Conflict and socioeconomic instability make education in Nigeria's unstable areas even more difficult. These issues include insufficient resources, frequent school closures, and displacement. The potential of Artificial Intelligence (AI) to address these issues and advance educational equity in countries impacted by war is examined in this study. In a survey of 400 stakeholders, which included administrators (13.2%), Teachers (44.7%), and students (34.2%). 73.7% of respondents named school closures as a major barrier, and 65% mentioned inadequate internet connectivity. Even while they acknowledged the advantages of AI, 68.4% of participants expressed a favorable opinion of AI's ability to enhance educational achievements, demonstrating that most people had a positive perception of it. To remove current obstacles and improve education in insecure areas, this paper emphasizes the critical need focused AI deployment tactics, infrastructure development, and professional development al organizations, and the private sector to work together to make sure AI adoption takes into account the particular difficulties these areas face.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Conflict-Affected Regions, Nigeria, AI Adoption Barriers

2025-FOE-ABS-V03

Assessment of Secondary School Science Teachers' Intention Towards Entrepreneurship Education in Minna Metropolis, Niger State

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to identify the influence of science teachers' intention towards Entrepreneurship education in senior secondary school Minna. The objectives of this study are to identify the level of teachers towards students'. This study examined the intention of science teachers towards entrepreneurship education in senior secondary schools Minna, Niger State. Two research questions guided the conduct of the study. The study adopted descriptive research design. The population of the study comprised science teachers in senior secondary schools Minna, Niger State. One hundred and fifty-six (156) (Male=100 and Female=56) respondents were randomly selected as sample for this study and were used for data analysis. The data was collected using teachers' intention toward Entrepreneurship with four-point Likert rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA)=4, Agree (A)=3, Disagree (D)=2 and Strongly Disagree (SD)=1. The instrument was validated by two experts using construct and criterion validity. The reliability coefficient of 0.88 was obtained using Cronbach alpha. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions. The result of this study shows that the average mean of 3.00 was used as the benchmark, therefore, the mean of 3.00 and above is considered 'Strong Intention' and any mean below 3.00 is considered 'Weak Intention'. Consequently, items 1 – 10 show an average mean of 3.27 to 4.11, indicating that secondary school teachers have strong entrepreneurship intentions. Also, the result indicates that male teachers have a mean entrepreneurial intention score of 37.66 with an SD of 3.97, while female teachers have a slightly lower mean score of 37.25 with an SD of 3.60. This difference implies that, there is no substantial disparity between genders regarding entrepreneurial intentions. The finding of this study shows that secondary school teachers has strong entrepreneurship intentions, teachers strongly agreed with entrepreneurial career attractiveness and the satisfaction derived from entrepreneurship. Also, the finding of this study shows that there was a small difference between the male and female teachers exhibit nearly identical levels of entrepreneurial intention, with only marginal variation in their scores. This small difference implies no substantial disparity between genders regarding entrepreneurial intentions. Based on the findings of this study, it was recommended that Schools should include entrepreneurship courses in their curricula and must ensure that all students regardless of their academic specialization study entrepreneurship.

Keywords: Entrepreneurship Education; Teacher's intention creativity; Innovative skills; Entrepreneurial capability; and Performance.

2025-FOE-ABS-V04

**Comparative Analysis of Psychological Outcomes Between Students in Conflict-Affected
and Secure Regions in Delta State, Nigeria**

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Abstract

This study carried out a comparative analysis of psychological outcomes between students in conflict-affected and secure regions. The investigation was guided by two objectives, research questions, and hypotheses. Utilizing a survey design, the study used a population of 28,065 students, with a sample of 394 students from conflict-affected and secure regions of Delta State, determined using the Taro Yamane formula for sample size calculation. The cluster sampling technique was used to select the students. A researcher-designed questionnaire titled Psychological Outcome Questionnaire (POQ) was used to gather the required data for the study. An expert in Measurement and Evaluation reviewed the questionnaire to ensure its validity. The questionnaires showed good internal consistency with a reliability coefficient of 0.835, determined by Cronbach's Alpha test. To answer the research questions, mean and standard deviation were used, while the independent t-test was used to test the hypotheses at the 0.05 level of significance. The findings of the study showed that there is a significant difference in the prevalence of psychological issues among students in conflict-affected and secure regions in Delta State, and there is a significant difference in the severity of psychological issues among students in conflict-affected and secure regions in Delta State. The two recommendations based on the two above findings are that the Delta State government should prioritize mental health support services in conflict-affected regions and implement targeted interventions to address the psychological issues faced by students in these areas. Also, to manage the severity of the psychological issues, the government should engage with local community leaders and organizations to provide holistic support to students in conflict-affected regions, including counselling, trauma-informed care, and psychosocial support.

Keywords: Comparative, Analysis, Psychological Outcome, Conflict-affected, Secure region

2025-FOE-ABS-V05

Ensuring Inclusive and High-Quality STEM Education amidst Security Challenges in Nigeria

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Abstract

STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education is essential for national development, equipping students with the skills needed for innovation, problem-solving, and technological advancement. However, in Nigeria, persistent insecurity—driven by insurgencies, banditry, and communal conflicts—has severely disrupted access to quality STEM education, particularly in conflict-prone regions. School closures, teacher shortages, gender disparities, and psychological trauma have exacerbated educational inequalities, disproportionately affecting students in rural areas and female learners. This paper explores the impact of insecurity on STEM education in Nigeria and proposes strategies to ensure its continuity amidst these challenges. Key solutions include leveraging digital learning platforms, enhancing school security measures, establishing alternative learning centers, and implementing teacher training programs to sustain quality instruction. Special attention is given to promoting gender-inclusive STEM policies to encourage female participation despite cultural and security-related barriers. Furthermore, the paper examines global best practices, drawing insights from Afghanistan's Community-Based Education (CBE) model and Kenya's Digital Literacy Program (DLP), which have successfully maintained educational access in conflict-prone regions. These models offer valuable lessons that can be adapted to the Nigerian context. By fostering public-private partnerships, investing in education technology, and implementing comprehensive security measures, Nigeria can build a resilient STEM education system that ensures inclusive, high-quality learning opportunities despite ongoing security challenges. A collaborative effort involving government agencies, educational institutions, private sector players, and international organizations is necessary to safeguard the future of STEM education in Nigeria.

Keywords: STEM education, insecurity, digital learning, school closures, teacher shortages, gender disparity.

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Evaluating Nigerian Universities' Teacher Education Programs Using the CIPP Model amidst Security Challenges

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Abstract

This study aimed to evaluate the quality of undergraduate teacher education programs in Nigerian universities in the context of the country's security challenges. A descriptive survey design was employed to collect relevant data, with the study guided by Stufflebeam's (1971) CIPP (Context, Input, Process, and Product) evaluation model. A structured questionnaire was developed, validated, and used for data collection. Data were analyzed using SPSS 25, with descriptive statistics applied for interpretation. The findings revealed that while undergraduate teacher education programs (UTED) in Nigerian universities exhibit some level of effectiveness in terms of context, input, process, and product, several areas require improvement. Specifically, admission criteria were found to be inadequate, the number of teaching staff was insufficient, and opportunities for continuous professional training were lacking. Additionally, modifications were needed in the compulsory courses, teaching and learning materials were insufficient, and students demonstrated limited ICT competencies. Based on these findings, the study concluded that while UTED is moderately effective in the face of insecurity in the country, revisions are necessary to improve its objectives, content, teaching methods, instructional materials, and assessment strategies to align with the current educational needs in Nigeria. The study recommended that relevant authorities provide sufficient and appropriate teaching and learning materials and recruit adequate teaching staff, among other improvements.

Keywords: undergraduate, evaluation, teacher education, program assessment, Nigerian universities

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Access, Equity and Quality of Guidance and Counselling Education in the Face of Insecurity

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Abstract

The study was conducted to determine access, equity and quality of guidance and counselling education in the face of insecurity in Nigeria. This research was descriptive in form. This design was used to gather information from a sampled of students. The population of the study comprised 3622 students in 44 secondary schools in Southern Ijaw Local Government Area of Bayelsa State. The sample of the study include 300 students of SSI – SSIII classes. The students were selected from 30 secondary schools because of the ease of accessibility of the schools. A structured questionnaire containing 17 items and validated by experts, was use for data collection. The data collected was analysed with the use of simple percentage and mean. The result indicated that guidance and counselling education are not accessible, not equitable and of poor quality due the inadequacy of counselling personnel, inadequate funding, unavailability of needed facilities etc. The paper concluded that the inadequacy gap in guidance and counselling education remains the major reason insecurity persist in our society. The paper recommends the provision of necessary tools to improve guidance and counselling services in our schools.

Key words: Access, Equity, Quality of Guidance and Counselling, Insecurity

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The Role of Technology in Enhancing STEM Education Access and Quality in Insecure Zones in Oyo State

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Abstract

Access to quality STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics) education remains a challenge in insecure areas, particularly in the Ibarapa Zone of Oyo State, Nigeria. This study explores how technology can enhance both the accessibility and quality of STEM education in such regions. Through a mixed-methods approach, data was collected from 50 STEM teachers across 15 schools in the Ibarapa Zone using questionnaires, while additional insights were gathered through interviews with both teachers and students. The study examines the role of digital learning tools, virtual classrooms, and other technological innovations in overcoming barriers posed by insecurity. Findings indicate that technology significantly improves learning opportunities by providing remote access to educational resources and fostering interactive learning experiences. However, the research also highlights challenges such as poor infrastructure, lack of teacher training, and limited internet connectivity. The study concludes with recommendations for policymakers and educators on integrating technology effectively to bridge educational gaps in insecure areas.

Keywords: Technology, STEM, Insecurity, Access, Quality

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**Administrating Children’s Spiritual Development in Early Childhood Care and Education Amidst
Insecurity in Nigeria**

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Abstract

Spirituality is addressed as an important aspect of young children’s holistic learning linking to autonomy, compassion, resilience, responsibility and well-being. Early childhood education is vital for building a sense of self-worth, confidence, and success in children. Spiritual development is integral to this process, contributing to the inculcation of sound moral values, feelings of joy, academic excellence, unity, and community development. This paper addresses the critical role of administrating spiritual development in early childhood care and education (ECCE) amidst Nigeria's challenging context of insecurity. It examines how educators can foster spiritual growth, promoting moral values, emotional well-being, and resilience in young children. The paper recommends among others the need for the government to monitor and evaluate the implementation of policies, ECCE curricula and the environment. Ensure that ECCE centres are safe and secure environments where children can learn and grow without fear.

Keywords: Administrating, Spiritual Development, Early Childhood Care and Education Insecurity.

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Access, Equity and Quality of Early Childhood Education in The Face of Insecurity in Northwest Nigeria

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Abstract

This article examines the impact of insecurity on access, equity and quality early childhood education in the face of insecurity in northwest Nigeria. Early childhood education program is now regarded as the foundation children's development and the key to the success of the whole education system in Nigeria. The early childhood education (ECE) is recognized by the Nigeria National Policy on Education (FRN 2013). In the Policy provisions were made stating the objectives and guidelines taken by the government to achieve the goals of this type of education. This article argues that despite the importance of education provided at early years of life, many Nigerian children are denied access to quality ECE due to insecurity, displacement and poverty. Hence, the article identifies destruction of schools, displacement of families, communal insecurity and lack of resources as some of the challenges faced by children, teachers and schools in conflict affected areas of northwest Nigeria. The article also discusses the consequences of insecurity on the cognitive, social and emotional development of young children. The article asserts that ensuring access, equity and quality of ECE is crucial for promoting peace, stability and economic development in Nigeria. The article suggests that policy makers and stakeholders in education to ensure that safe, inclusive and quality ECE is provided in security challenged communities in Nigeria.

Keywords: early childhood education, access, equity, quality, insecurity, Nigeria.

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Quality of Educational Guidance and Counseling in The Face of Insecurity in Gusau Zamfara State

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ABSTRACT

The study of access equity and quality of guidance and counseling in the face of in security in Nigeria aimed at finding solution to insecurity more especially in the North-west of the country. The insecurity is significantly increasing and become a challenge, especially in the context of progress. Nigeria has faced widespread security concerns in recent years, including terrorism, kidnapping, banditry, and communal violence, which have affected both rural and urban areas. These issues create obstacles for the provision of guidance and counseling services particularly in the affected areas. Though guidance and counseling are essential elements in discipline management of people in all societies even the most primitive societies grew out the of the necessity of guiding individual's behavior patterns in the interest of the societies even the society cannot function without the exercise of discipline. Using guidance and counseling to enhance discipline and modify deviant or abnormal behavior in the society must be intensifying. It is absolutely necessary to energize the provision of guidance and counseling services with qualitative personal in modifying the deviant behavior. Guidance and counseling program must duel on finding a lasting solution to the people resides in insecurity places such as: counseling for trauma, depression, and bereavement counseling.